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WELCOME

to the conference **Colonial Pasts, New Approaches and Historiographical Futures** organized by the digital infrastructure project GLOBALISE. The conference is part of our endeavor to build a research environment that unlocks the crucial Copied Letters (OBP) series of the colonial archive of the Dutch East India Company for interested societal and scientific audiences worldwide.

We are excited to welcome so many researchers, heritage specialists, artists, citizen scientists and others from different parts of the globe. This fits with our belief that the making of a digital infrastructure needs dedicated teamwork, but that this cannot be done without involving the users it should cater to. It is our mission to develop an infrastructure that does not just provide easy access to the text-recognized archives, but to embed this in high quality historical contextualization and critical narratives that provide an ethically-guided lens on the information in colonial archives. We hope that in this way our infrastructure can help to foster new, diverse, and more representative histories based on the VOC archives.

This is crucial, because these extensive and detailed colonial archives are invaluable for studying not only the world of the VOC itself, but also for the often under-documented societies of early modern Africa, Asia, and Australia. They shed light on the many local, regional, and global interactions between these regions. This renders it all the more important that the information in the archives – from the gruesome and violent encounters to the happy histories, from the seemingly simple international loanwords to the most complex concepts – become accessible for the largest and most diverse audiences possible. It also means that in unlocking the archive, there is need to consider the manifold interpretations possible – to not to allow for an ‘anything goes’-type of history writing, but to instead fuel a critical, responsible and rigorously researched re-engagement with colonial histories and archives. Challenging the enduring colonial biases and legacies needs to be done through a multiplicity of perspectives, hence the conference subtitle which emphasizes the need for new historiographical agendas and trajectories.

As societies across the globe face the increasing challenges of ideological violence, nationalism, xenophobia and rising authoritarian movements, in many ways facilitated by the powers and algorithms of anti-democratic commercial big tech, we are confronted now more than ever by the fact that digital resources, tools and infrastructure are not neutral. The world of digital possibilities – from linking techniques, to data and AI – is riddled with bias and uninformed or often even deliberate deflections. This is not unlike the archive and the historical and societal narratives and discourses in which the interpretation of these sources are embedded. And indeed, the humanities, history and the archival discipline have long traditions of confronting this.

This is a pertinent reminder that the extremism and violence the world faces amidst present-day geopolitical transformations do not render projects on historical research and archival infrastructure irrelevant. On the contrary, the manner in which we undertake these projects and the resources we make available can become powerful tools to challenge the narratives that mobilize these transformations. This should urge everyone to step up and to contribute, to reflect and explore how we can make archives, data, research tools and the histories that are written with it more inclusive, critical, responsible and engaging. And perhaps – through these new histories – we can provide new understandings of colonial, local and world histories, and their legacies, that help to build bridges and help to encourage people to make the world a better place.

On behalf of the GLOBALISE team and many other colleagues who made this conference possible,

We wish you a good conference!

Melinda Susanto, Manjusha Kuruppath, Matthias van Rossum

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CONFERENCE SCHEDULE

DAY 0

Tuesday, 3 March 2026

Time	Event	Venue
13.00 – 13.15	Welcome and coffee	<i>Vide</i>
13.15 – 14.15	Getting to know GLOBALISE sessions 1-3	<i>Parallel rooms</i>
14.15 – 14.30	Short break	<i>Vide</i>
14.30 – 15.30	Getting to know GLOBALISE sessions 1-3	<i>Parallel rooms</i>
15.30 – 17.00	Dutch East India Company in Amsterdam Walk, led by Rizky Kalebos	<i>Meeting point: registration desk.</i>

DAY 1

Wednesday, 4 March 2026

Time	Event	Venue
08.30 – 10.00	Registration and coffee	<i>Entry Hall & Vide</i>
09.00 – 10.00	Getting to know GLOBALISE sessions 1-3	<i>Parallel rooms</i>

Conference Schedule

Time	Event	Venue
10.15 – 10.30	Short welcome	<i>Max Nettleau</i>
10.30 – 12.00	Parallel session 1	<i>Parallel rooms</i>
12.00 – 13.00	Lunch	<i>Max Nettleau/Vide</i>
13.00 – 14.00	Keynote Lecture: Matthias van Rossum	<i>Max Nettleau</i>
14.00 – 14.45	GLOBALISE project update	<i>Max Nettleau</i>
14.45 – 15.00	Short break	<i>Max Nettleau/Vide</i>
15.00 – 16.30	Parallel session 2	<i>Parallel rooms</i>
15.00 – 16.30	Outsmarting the Machine Workshop	<i>Souvarine</i>
16.30 – 16.45	Short break	<i>Max Nettleau/Vide</i>
16.45 – 17.00	Short reflection on Day 1	<i>Max Nettleau</i>
17.00 – 18.00	Roundtable 1: Global Histories and the Digital Turn	<i>Max Nettleau</i>
18.00 – 18.30	TogetherTogether: Acero, Catani & Gaspar <i>Farewell: An Imagined Response to Dutch Colonizers.</i>	<i>Meeting point: registration desk</i>
18.00 – 19.30	Drinks	<i>Max Nettleau</i>

Conference Schedule

DAY 2

Thursday, 5 March 2026

Time		Venue
09.00 – 10.40	Parallel session 3	<i>Parallel rooms</i>
10.45 – 12.00	Keynote Lecture: Ann Stoler	<i>Max Nettlau</i>
12.00 – 12.30	Short lunch	<i>Max Nettlau/Vide</i>
12.30 – 13.00	Roelof Petrus van Wyk AN UNNATURAL HISTORY, A Performance Lecture. <i>Fugitive Desire under VOC Capitalist Erasure, made legible with Artistic Research methods by excavating the Sodomy Criminal Case records in the Colonial VOC Archive, Cape Town, 1652-1795.</i>	<i>Posthumus</i>
12.30 – 13.00	Carmen Draxler »Mother-of-Oil« <i>Colonial roots of the oil company Shell in Indonesia.</i>	<i>Meeting point: registration desk</i>
13.00 – 14.30	Parallel session 4	<i>Parallel rooms</i>
13.30 – 14.00	Carmen Draxler »Mother-of-Oil« <i>Colonial roots of the oil company Shell in Indonesia.</i>	<i>Meeting point: registration desk</i>
14.30 – 15.00	Coffee break	<i>Max Nettlau/Vide</i>
14.30 – 15.00	Carmen Draxler »Mother-of-Oil« <i>Colonial roots of the oil company Shell in Indonesia.</i>	<i>Meeting point: registration desk</i>

Conference Schedule

Time	Event	Venue
15.00 – 16.45	Parallel session 5	<i>Parallel rooms</i>
16.45 – 17.00	Short break	<i>Max Nettleau/Vide</i>
17.00 – 17.15	Short reflection on Day 2	<i>Max Nettleau</i>
17.15 – 18.30	Roundtable 2: Decolonizing Infrastructure, Engaging Communities	<i>Max Nettleau</i>
19.30	Conference Dinner	<i>Kompaszaal</i>

DAY 3

Friday, 6 March 2026

Time	Event	Venue
09.00 – 10.45	Parallel session 6	<i>Parallel rooms</i>
09.00 – 10.30	Outsmarting the Machine Workshop	<i>Souvarine</i>
10.45 – 11.00	Short break	<i>Max Nettleau</i>
11.00 – 12.00	Keynote Lecture: Tonio Andrade	<i>Max Nettleau</i>
12.00 – 13.30	Closing Roundtable and Plenary Reflection	<i>Max Nettleau</i>
13.30 – 14.30	Lunch	<i>Max Nettleau/Vide</i>

KEYNOTE LECTURES

DAY 1

Wed 4 March 13.00 - 14.00
Max Nettlau room

KEYNOTE LECTURE 1: RESISTING EMPIRE! REFLECTIONS ON COLONIALISM, HISTORIOGRAPHY AND DIGITAL INFRASTRUCTURE

From mutinies to marronage, amok and complaint olas. This lecture tries to grapple with the many traces of histories of resistance that can be found in the archives of the Dutch East India Company. It questions how underexplored histories of resistance, violence and exploitation can help to revisit how we understand the history of colonialism and its impact on societies across the globe, and it uses this lens to reflect on the potential and risks of the rapid developments in digital infrastructure for colonial archives.

MATTHIAS VAN ROSSUM

Project leader GLOBALISE

Matthias van Rossum is Senior Researcher at the International Institute of Social History (IISH) in Amsterdam and professor of Global Histories of Labour and Colonialism at the Radboud University in Nijmegen. He is project leader of the GLOBALISE project for digital infrastructure of the Dutch East India Company archives, as well as the research projects Resisting Enslavement (NWO Vidi) and Voices of Enslavement (ERC CoG).

DAY 2

Thu 5 March 10.45 - 12.00
Max Nettlau room

KEYNOTE LECTURE 2: ON BEARING ARCHIVAL TRUTHS - THEIR BURDENS OF COLONIAL PROOF

This reflection derives from decades working on the politics of truth in shaping imperial governance and its hierarchies of credibility, as manifest in Dutch and French colonial contexts of the late 19th and early 20th century. It's a project that asks how those who govern know what they know, how arbitrators of truth imagine how they know, what constitutes evidence of what they profess to know, and what they claim as proof when what they profess to know, they do not.

If the archival documents are, as the luminous French feminist historian Arlette Farge once argued, "a tear in the fabric of time, an unplanned glimpse offered into an unexpected event," they are indeed as much a tear in the fiction of reason, often in collision with the regimes of truth that dictate causal arrows and linear sequence, closer to how Foucault defined an event, as a breach of the self-evident and common sense.

In this reflection, I call upon a set of scenes where "proof" and "truth" put demands on what is known, by whom, how and in what way. In pursuing micro-fissures in the edifice of imperial rule, I turn to sense and sensibility, to the texture of the detail shaping what we think we know of imperial formations past and present, and among those with resurgent and recursive durabilities today.

ANN LAURA STOLER

Willy Brandt Distinguished Professor of Anthropology and History

Ann Laura Stoler is Willy Brandt Distinguished University Professor of Historical Studies and Anthropology at The New School for Social Research where she is founding director of The Institute for Critical Social Inquiry and founding co-editor of journal, *Political Concepts: A Critical Lexicon*.

Her work on the politics of archives, imperial debris, a colonial reading of Foucault's *History of Sexuality*, on grammars of time, and the politics of sentiment have been guided by an effort to understand and confront the hypervisibility and invisibility of infrastructures of inequality. Her books include *Along the Archival Grain: Epistemic Anxieties and Colonial Common Sense*.

DAY 3

Fri 6 March 11.00 - 12.00
Max Nettlau room

KEYNOTE LECTURE 3: THE ART AND PERIL OF BEING IN BETWEEN: REFLECTIONS ON CULTURAL BROKERS AND THE DUTCH EAST INDIA COMPANY

Scholars have long recognized the Dutch East India Company's dependence on local translators and cultural mediators. In this talk I plan to discuss three such figures who were active between 1633 and 1674: Krotoa Eva of the Cape of Good Hope, Osoet Pegua of Ayutthaya (Siam), and He Bin of Taiwan. Although they worked in vastly different contexts and faced unique challenges, their lives followed similar trajectories. Each rose to influence through linguistic and cultural skills that enabled them to mediate between Company officials and local populations. Each cultivated personal ties with Company officials that bypassed formal oversight. Each used these connections to accumulate wealth and influence, skillfully navigating internal fissures within both Company administration and local society. And each got into trouble with the Company on one hand and local groups on the other. This trouble generated documents – legal proceedings, seized letters, interrogations, and reports – that open a window onto the Company's messy realities on the ground, reminding us of the importance of personal networks, unofficial dealings, and intimate relations to the entangled histories of the VOC and the societies it operated within.

TONIO ANDRADE

Professor of Chinese and Global History at Emory University

Tonio Andrade is Professor of Chinese and Global History at Emory University. His major books include *The Last Embassy: The Dutch Mission of 1795 and the Forgotten History of Western Encounters with China* (Princeton, 2021), *The Gunpowder Age: China, Military Innovation, and the Rise of the West in World History* (Princeton, 2016), *Lost Colony: The Untold Story of Europe's First War with China* (Princeton, 2011), and *How Taiwan Became Chinese* (Columbia University Press, 2007). Honors include The John Simon Guggenheim Fellowship, The N.E.H. Public Scholars Fellowship, The Harry Frank Guggenheim Fellowship, and the American Historical Association's Gutenberg-e Prize. He lives in Decatur, Georgia, with his family and enjoys advocating for safe and sustainable transportation.

ROUNDTABLES

DAY 1

Wed 4 March 17.00 - 18.00
Max Nettlau room

ROUNDTABLE 1: GLOBAL HISTORIES AND THE DIGITAL TURN

The key question we envision is: How can large archival, data and research projects reshape the practice and impact of global history writing?

This round table aims to bring together leading scholars with related initiatives to the GLOBALISE project to discuss how these undertakings can fuel the field of global history through the accessibility of sources, the development of new research methods, and more.

CHAIR: GUIDO VAN MEERSBERGEN

University of Warwick and Journal of Global History

Guido van Meersbergen is an Associate Professor in Early Modern Global History at the University of Warwick, where he served as the director of the Global History and Culture Centre (2021-2025). He is a co-editor of the Journal of Global History and a coordinator of the Global Diplomacy Network. His research focuses on the presence of the Dutch and English East India Companies in South Asia, early modern diplomacy, and global travel. He is the author of *Ethnography and Encounter: The Dutch and English East India Companies in Seventeenth-Century South Asia* (Brill: 2022) and co-editor of *Trading Companies and Travel Knowledge in the Early Modern World* (Routledge: 2022). He recently co-edited a special issue of *Studies in Travel Writing* on "Travel Studies and the Decolonial Turn" (2024).

SPEAKER: DAGMAR FREIST

Carl-von-Ossietzky Universität Oldenburg, Prize Papers Project

Dagmar Freist is Professor of Early Modern History at UOL since 2004. Her research focuses on early modern global history, religious diversity and social practices, with special expertise in material history and digital humanities. She did her PhD at Cambridge University, and was a postdoc at the German Historical Institute in London. She was PI of the HERA project "Intoxicating Spaces". Since 2018, she is leading the long-term academy project "Prize Papers," in which multilingual documents and artefacts from colonial contexts are recorded and digitized; she is also spokesperson for the DiViAS and the ProSaDi project, a cooperation of humanities, data science, geoinformatics, and 3D analysis.

SPEAKER: ANA SOFIA RIBEIRO

Universidade de Évora, MONSOON project

ANA SOFIA RIBEIRO (Porto, 1982) is an Assistant Researcher at Évora University, Portugal since 2019. She holds a PhD in History of the University of Porto (2011) where she also obtained her History degree in 2005. Between 2012 and 2018 she held two post-doc positions at Évora University with projects related with collaborative trading networks in Iberian overseas empires during the period of the Habsburg Portugal (1580-1640). Her research focus in the early modern Iberian trade and finance networks, early modern violence, digital humanities. She is the PI of the project MONSOON: The Habsburg Estado da Índia in a Digital Perspective (1605-1624), funded by FCT.

SPEAKER: CLAUDE CHEVALEYRE

ENS de Lyon, China Human Trafficking and Slaving Database

Claude Chevaleyre is a CNRS Research Fellow at the Lyons Institute of East Asian Studies (IAO) and an Associate of the Bonn Center for Dependency and Slavery Studies. He holds a PhD from the EHESS and is an INALCO graduate. His research focuses on the social history of coerced labor in early modern China (15th–19th centuries). He is the principal investigator for the "China Human Trafficking and Slaving Database" and a member of the "Exploring Slave Trade in Asia" project. Additionally, he serves as Co-Editor-in-Chief of the journal *Études chinoises*.

ROUNDTABLE 2: DECOLONIZING INFRASTRUCTURE, ENGAGING COMMUNITIES

How can new digital methods and infrastructures unsettle colonial ways of knowing and open possibilities for more decolonial forms of engagement?

This roundtable brings together speakers representing communities across the globe as well as scholars working with communities and engaged with archival practices. Together, we invite reflections on how archival infrastructures affect access to colonial archives, past and present. What does increased digital accessibility mean for communities with a stake in colonial archives? How might digital infrastructures move towards practices of care?

CHAIR: WIM MANUHUTU

VU University Amsterdam

Wim Manuhutu is a historian, curator and a heritage professional. He studied at Utrecht University where he specialized in the colonial and postcolonial history of Indonesia, and the Maluku region in particular. He worked as the director of the Moluccan museum and as a freelance curator and advisor in the heritage sector. Manuhutu is a lecturer in the History department of the VU Universiteit Amsterdam, teaching courses on Dutch, European and colonial history. His current research focuses on the histories of slavery in East Indonesia and its aftermath.

SPEAKER: ASAWARI LUTHRA

Historian and anthropologist, Design Academy Eindhoven

Asawari Luthra currently teaches Anthropology at the Design Academy Eindhoven. Trained as a historian and anthropologist, she worked with the GLOBALISE project, interviewing archivists, historians, curators, artists, and community members across the Global North and South. Her question was simple: how do we make digital colonial archives truly accessible for the communities whose ancestors appear in them? The answer, she found, goes beyond putting documents online. It means adding warnings and context about disturbing content, offering emotional support, and creating space for communities to tell their own stories—to reclaim narratives once written without them. Her research seeks to ensure that digitisation serves not just access, but justice and healing.

SPEAKER: YUS BROERSMA

Heritage practitioner and researcher

Born and raised in East Java, Indonesia, Yus is a heritage practitioner and researcher who speaks from the position of a source community. Living and working across the Global South and Global North has shaped her strong interest in dialogue, positionality, and the power relations embedded in heritage practices. She has worked with the Indonesian Heritage Society at Museum Nasional Jakarta and is currently involved in the RECONCILE project (EU–South Africa–Indonesia), which rethinks museum collections and narratives through inclusive and decolonial approaches. Yus is committed to humanising museums and archives by creating space for communities to articulate and negotiate their own histories and knowledge systems.

SPEAKER: WISAAL ABRAHAMS

Stellenbosch University, Manvrou Collective

Wisaal Abrahams is a South African artist, researcher, and consultant working at the intersection of heritage, social justice, and innovation. A Master of Visual Arts candidate at Stellenbosch University, she specializes in Cape colonial history, slavery, and Khoisan legacies. As Founder of the Manvrou Collective, Wisaal also serves as a community mediator and coach. She consults for the KKKA and The Castle of Good Hope, bridging archives with technology. A former Global Slavery Fellow (IISG Amsterdam), Wisaal leads multi-disciplinary initiatives like Frequency of Freedom and De Halve Reis, dedicated to honoring slave heritage through community-focused, restorative storytelling.

SPEAKER: CHARLES JEURGENS

University of Amsterdam

Charles Jeurgens is professor of archival studies at the University of Amsterdam. He has published extensively on the creation of records by various Dutch colonial administrative bodies, and on the ways in which these archives are made accessible and made available to the public by archivists. His particular interest lies in the question of how decoloniality can be translated into an archival practice that does justice to marginalized perspectives, historical inequality, and the ongoing impact of colonial power relations.

SPEAKER: YOSHIHARU OKAYAMA

Secretary-General of the Dutch Trading Post Heritage Network

Yoshiharu Okayama was born in Hirado in 1962. He joined the Matsura Historical Museum in 1988 as a curator in 2011 and oversaw the opening of the restored 1639 warehouse of the Hirado Dutch Trading Post, reconstructed by the City of Hirado. In 2013, Yoshiharu Okayama was appointed Director of both the Matsura Historical Museum and the Hirado Dutch Trading Post.

With the reopening of the reconstructed 1639 warehouse of the Hirado Dutch Trading Post in 2011, he recognized the importance of engaging with international scholarship on the Dutch East India Company. In 2014, he established the Asian Dutch Trading Post Heritage Network, bringing together institutions across Asia connected to former Dutch trading posts. Since then, annual meetings and research workshops have been held on a rotating basis among member regions. Last year, contributions from ten members were compiled into a booklet.

PLENARY DISCUSSION AND CLOSING ROUNDTABLE 3: COLONIAL PASTS, EMPOWERING FUTURES

How is digitization transforming the kinds of questions we can ask of colonial archives? What new research directions seem most urgent or promising after this conference, and what missing perspectives have become visible?

During this conference, speakers will have explored diverse ways to interpret and write new histories using the archives of the Dutch East India Company and beyond. The key themes of this conference are: the VOC archives and history writing, the VOC as a colonial power, decentring histories of the VOC, digital approaches and the colonial archives.

In this final roundtable, we envision an open discussion between panelists and conference attendees, inviting you to share your insights and to reflect collectively on how global history writing can move forward.

CHAIR: LODEWIJK PETRAM

Project manager GLOBALISE

Lodewijk Petram is the project manager of Globalise. He holds a PhD in economic history and is a senior researcher at the Huygens Institute. His publications include *The World's First Stock Exchange* (2014), a financial history with a central role for the VOC. He currently leads a new collaborative project with Erasmus University Rotterdam's School of Economics that uses the Globalise research infrastructure to investigate the long-term impact of early Dutch colonialism in Asia.

SPEAKER: MATTHIAS VAN ROSSUM

Project leader GLOBALISE

Matthias van Rossum is Senior Researcher at the International Institute of Social History (IISH) in Amsterdam and professor of Global Histories of Labour and Colonialism at the Radboud University in Nijmegen. He is project leader of the GLOBALISE project for digital infrastructure of the Dutch East India Company archives, as well as the research projects *Resisting Enslavement* (NWO Vidi) and *Voices of Enslavement* (ERC CoG).

SPEAKER: LIJA JOSEPH

Leiden University

Lija Mary Kambakkaran Joseph is a Cosmos Malabaricus Fellow of Colonial and Global History at the University of Leiden, where she is part of the broader project of decolonization of Dutch Archives. Holding also an MA from the Centre For Historical Studies, Jawaharlal Nehru University (JNU), her primary research area is maritime social and cultural history, with a focus of historicizing transnational cultural exchanges and negotiations of Christianity in the Indian Ocean and beyond. Currently, in Leiden, her work examines the Malabar society during the transition from the Portuguese to the Dutch period, with a focus on questions of intra-religious power dynamics, influence of caste and cultural expressions.

SPEAKER: ANNA BRUINS

University of Warwick

Anna Bruins is a historian of science, holding master's degrees from Utrecht University and the University of Glasgow. She started her PhD at the University of Warwick in 2024. Her research project, provisionally titled *In Pursuit of Planting: Scientific Travel and the VOC's Bioprospective Quest in the Indian Ocean World*, focuses on the production of natural knowledge by VOC travellers, and their contributions to the rise of the Company's plantation industries. Using a diverse range of travel writing, her research explores human-nonhuman relations. It pays particular attention to the colonial conceptualisation of nature in terms of ownership, value, and progress.

SPEAKER: LUC BULTEN

Radboud University Nijmegen

Luc Bulten is a postdoctoral fellow in Sri Lankan History at the University of Cambridge, and affiliated with Queens' College as postdoctoral research associate. He also holds a position at Radboud University in Nijmegen as an assistant professor of social and economic history. In his work, Luc is especially interested in local-colonial interactions in South and Southeast Asia related to labour regimes, land tenure, family history, tax farming, intra-Asian trade, the environment and the reciprocal production of knowledge and institutions.

SPEAKER: WENRUI ZHAO

University of Utah

Wenrui Zhao is a historian of science and medicine, with a focus on early modern northern Europe and its connections with the wider world, particularly Asia. She is an assistant professor at the University of Utah. Her current project studies the VOC's mining venture in Sumatra in the late seventeenth and early eighteenth centuries.

OVERVIEW OF PANELS

SESSION 1

Wed 4 March 10.30 - 12.00

<p>Session 1A: Material Culture and Social Life</p> <p><i>Nikolaevsky room</i></p> <p><i>Chair:</i> Tristan Mostert, Leiden University <i>Session coordinator:</i> Nur'Ain Taha, Utrecht University</p>	<p>Session 1B: Mobilities</p> <p><i>Max Nettleau room</i></p> <p><i>Chair:</i> Marieke Hendriksen, Huygens Institute <i>Session coordinator:</i> Bente de Leede, Leiden University</p>	<p>Session 1C: Digital Humanities Approaches to the VOC Archive</p> <p><i>Posthumus room</i></p> <p><i>Chair:</i> Stella Verkijk, Huygens Institute & VU University Amsterdam <i>Session Coordinator:</i> Bethany Warner, International Institute of Social History</p>
<p>Josephine Koopman (European University Institute, Florence) - Unboxing the Dutch East India Company Archives: on the material culture of betel chewing.</p> <p>Isabelle Stone (The Open University and The Museum of the Home, London) - Collecting Shells at a Cost: Johan Nieuwhof's Account of the Pearl and Chank Shell Fishery at Toothukudi, 1664-1665.</p> <p>Lodewijk J. Wagenaar (Independent scholar) - Character and remains of the VOC colony of Ceylon. An internet search.</p>	<p>Roni Tabroni (National Research and Innovation Agency, Indonesia) - The Nusantara Hajj Pilgrimage in the 17th and 18th centuries: The Emergence of a Global Ummah Identity.</p> <p>Nikhil Bellarykar (Independent scholar) - Maratha overseas trade in the 17th century- tracing the ship Shambhu Prasad through the VOC archives.</p> <p>Tom Hoogervorst (KITLV) - Globalise and Unlocked Food Archives.</p>	<p>Willemien de Kock (University of Groningen), Emin Tatar (University of Groningen), and Rob Lenders (Radboud University Nijmegen) - Tracing Historical Tortoiseshell Exploitation and Trade through AI-Driven Analysis.</p> <p>Shuai Wang (Utrecht University), Andre Valdestilhas (VU University Amsterdam), Ronald Siebes (VU University Amsterdam), and Angelica Maineri (ODISSEI) - Aggregating the FAIR Assessment Results of Datasets by the GLOBALISE Community for Evaluating FAIR Data Management.</p>

SESSION 2

Wed 4 March 15.00 - 16.30

<p>Session 2A: The Dutch Reformed Church and Colonialism <i>Nikolaevsky room</i></p> <p><i>Chair:</i> Dienke Hondius, VU University Amsterdam <i>Session coordinator:</i> Bente de Leede, Leiden University</p>	<p>Session 2B: Trade, Colonial Expansion and Glocal Networks <i>Max Nettleau room</i></p> <p><i>Chair:</i> Erik Odegard, International Institute of Social History <i>Session coordinator:</i> Britt van Duijvenvoorde, International Institute of Social History</p>	<p>Session 2C: Currencies, Politics and Labour <i>Posthumus room</i></p> <p><i>Chair:</i> Maarten Manse, Linnaeus University <i>Session coordinator:</i> Vany Susanto, University of Amsterdam</p>
<p>Jon Kuiper (University of Groningen) - The Dutch Reformed Church on Ambon (1605-1700): Creating Power Structures and Framing the Other.</p> <p>Yudha Thianto (Calvin Theological Seminary, USA) - The VOC, the Church, and the Massacre of Banda in 1621.</p> <p>Fred van Lieburg (VU University Amsterdam) - A New Biographical Dictionary of Netherlands Indian Ministers, Sick-comforters and Missionaries 1600-1960.</p>	<p>Ajay Joy Mathew (Mahatma Gandhi University, India) - Between the Cartaz and the Zeebrief: The Zamorin's Maritime Diplomacy, 1633-1766.</p> <p>Luc Bulten (Radboud University Nijmegen) - The Making of Colombo: Dutch and Lankan Engineering, Infrastructures and Commodity Trade, 1745-1795.</p> <p>Marsely Kehoe (Independent scholar) - Exploring Global Textile Circulation with the Dutch Textile Trade Project.</p>	<p>Nurman Kholis (National Research and Innovation Agency, Indonesia) - "Duit" and "Dirham": A Preliminary Study on The Arabic Scripts in VOC-Dutch East India Coins in Java in 18th and 19th Centuries.</p> <p>Maarten Draper (European University Institute, Florence) - The Travails of Paper Currency in the Dutch Indian Ocean, 1780-1825.</p> <p>Jan Lucassen (International Institute of Social History) - The deep monetization of India and changing labour relations 1500-1900.</p>

SESSION 3

Thu 5 March 09.00 - 10.40

<p>Session 3A: Mediators, Knowledge and Contestation (Hybrid) <i>Nikolaevsky room</i></p> <p><i>Chair:</i> Jos Gommans, Leiden University <i>Session coordinator:</i> Muhammad Asyrafi, Leiden University</p>	<p>Session 3B: Global-Micro Histories and Colonial Structure <i>Max Nettleau room</i></p> <p><i>Chair:</i> Nira Wickramasinghe, Leiden University <i>Session coordinator:</i> Britt van Duijvenvoorde, International Institute of Social History</p>	<p>Session 3C: (Re)Connecting Histories across Borders <i>Posthumus room</i></p> <p><i>Chair:</i> Pepijn Brandon, International Institute of Social History <i>Session coordinator:</i> Bethany Warner, International Institute of Social History</p>
<p>Michael C. Reidy (Australian Catholic University, Melbourne) - Locally-based intermediaries and foreign agents during the VOC's slave trading commissions in the eighteenth-century Indian Ocean.</p> <p>Huang Xianting (University of Macau) - Circulation of Camphor in the VOC World: Trade, Knowledge and Representation in Networks.</p> <p>Romé van Oostenbrugge (Utrecht University) - At the Margins of European Knowledge: Local Guides' Contributions to VOC Navigation During the Eighteenth Century.</p> <p>Maarten Manse (Linnaeus University) - Recasting the Terms of Empire: Indigenous Translators and Scribes in the VOC Archives, and how they mediated the legal vocabulary through Treaty Making in Southeast Asia.</p>	<p>Byapti Sur (Thapar Institute of Engineering and Technology, India) - Local Lives, Global Stories: Studying the VOC Factories in Bengal, 1600-1800.</p> <p>Rivindu de Zoysa (University of Colombo, Sri Lanka) - Carel de Mirande: A Microhistory of the Service of an Administrative Official in Dutch Ceylon.</p> <p>Ann Heylen (National Taiwan Normal University) - Women in the VOC Archive: Patriarchy and Presence in Dutch Formosa.</p> <p>Rosalie Oudshoorn (Leiden University) - Succession, adoption, and power: Ranis in Malabar during the Dutch period.</p>	<p>Guido Van Meersbergen (University of Warwick) - Tracing Diplomatic Intermediaries in the VOC archives.</p> <p>Zhonghua Du (University of Amsterdam) - Planting Addictions: Opium Trade and the Colonial Expansion of the VOC in Asia.</p> <p>Nicholas C. Sy (University of Philippines Diliman & Radboud University Nijmegen) - The Asian Enslaved at the Intersections between European Archives, ca. 1663.</p>

SESSION 4

Thu 5 March 13.00 - 14.30

<p>Session 4A: Memory, Culture and the Archive</p> <p><i>Nikolaevsky room</i></p> <p><i>Chair:</i> Lotte Baltussen, Huygens Institute <i>Session coordinator:</i> Bethany Warner, International Institute of Social History</p>	<p>Session 4B: Local Diversities and Colonial Tensions</p> <p><i>Max Nettle room</i></p> <p><i>Chair:</i> Kathryn Wellen, KITLV <i>Session coordinator:</i> Louie Buana, Leiden University/KITLV</p>	<p>Session 4C: Commodity Frontiers, Environment and Resistance</p> <p>Posthumus room</p> <p><i>Chair:</i> Catia Antunes, Leiden University <i>Session coordinator:</i> Pichayapat Naisupap, Leiden University</p>
<p>Dondy Pepito Ramos (Australian Catholic University & University of the Philippines Diliman) - From Archives to Artefacts: Negotiating VOC Cultural Memories in Australia through the Dutch Shipwreck Artefacts.</p> <p>Nelo A. Schmalen (European-University Flensburg, Germany) - Decentering Colonial Histories through the City as an Archive.</p> <p>Prabhakar Garag (Independent scholar) - Unravelling Lifeworlds: Farmers and Consumers of Black Pepper.</p>	<p>Lap Kan Au (National Taiwan Normal University) - The Two Fates of Plural Societies Reconsidered: Actor-Centered Performative Reproduction of VOC Plakkaaten in Seventeenth-Century Cape and Formosa.</p> <p>Benjamin J.Q. Khoo (Independent scholar) - Murder in the Plantations: The Chinese Civil War on Riau (1786-92).</p> <p>Lija Mary Kambakaran Joseph (Leiden University) - Mapping the Everyday Lives of a Subaltern Community: The Mukkuvas of Malabar in the VOC Archives.</p>	<p>Jens Aurich (International Institute of Social History & University of Amsterdam) - By All Means Necessary: The Organization of Indigo Production and Resistance under the VOC.</p> <p>Linu Danielkutty (Utrecht University) - Spice Routes to Scarred Landscapes: How Dutch Colonial Corporation reshaped world landscapes.</p> <p>Kathleen Burke (Instituto Ciências Sociais, Lisbon) - Trans-imperial Travels: The Quest to Commodify Cacao in Island Southeast Asia.</p>

SESSION 5

Thu 5 March 15.00 - 16.45

<p>Session 5A: Material Culture and Diplomacy</p> <p><i>Nikolaevsky room</i></p> <p><i>Chair:</i> Alicia Schrikker, Leiden University <i>Session coordinator:</i> Pepijn Trienekens, International Institute of Social History</p>	<p>Session 5B: Colonial Extraction and Biopower</p> <p><i>Max Nettleau room</i></p> <p><i>Chair:</i> Joris van den Tol, Radboud University Nijmegen <i>Session coordinator:</i> Ryhan M. Yazid, Kyoto University/KITLV</p>	<p>Session 5C: Science, Environment, and Colonial Histories</p> <p><i>Posthumus room</i></p> <p><i>Chair:</i> Jessie Wei-Hsuan Chen, Huygens Institute <i>Session coordinator:</i> Nur'Ain Taha, Utrecht University</p>
<p>Pham Thuy Dung (Huygens Institute) - Symbolic Adoption of Dutch East India Company Merchants: Two Cases from Seventeenth-Century Vietnam.</p> <p>Ziquan Zhou (London School of Economics and Political Science) - Sappanwood for the King's Debt: Material and the Struggling Cooperation between the VOC and the Siamese Court in the Early Eighteenth Century.</p> <p>Philipp Huber (International Institute of Social History & Radboud University Nijmegen) - All Political Power comes from the Barrel of a Gun: Arms Trading, Gun Control, and Revolt in Ayutthaya, 1656-1709.</p>	<p>Wenrui Zhao (University of Utah) - A Female Alchemist and VOC's Mining Venture in Seventeenth-Century Sumatra.</p> <p>Sandunika Hasangani (Open University Sri Lanka) - The Politics of Healing: Medicine, Biopolitics, and the Dutch East India Company in Sri Lanka.</p> <p>Kate Ekama (Stellenbosch University) and VU Uarie Lehner (Bonn Center for Dependency and Slavery Studies) - Slavery and Dis/Ability: Case Studies from the Cape Colony.</p> <p>Britt van Duijvenvoorde (International Institute of Social History) - Mobilizing against mobilization: resistance against commercial enslavement in Arakan, Coromandel, and Malabar.</p>	<p>Aparajita Das (University of California, Berkeley) - Unsmooth Sailing in Swalley: The VOC's Hydrographies of Local Waterscapes in the Indian Ocean World.</p> <p>Anna Bruins (University of Warwick) - No (Hu)man is an Island: The Construction of Nature in Sources from Dutch Mauritius (1598-1710).</p> <p>Pichayapat Naisupap (Leiden University) - Through the life of Chillie, a Female Hunting Elephant: Uncovering the Glocal World of the 'Underclass' Elephants in Dutch Ceylon.</p> <p>Linda Robertus (Radboud University Nijmegen) - Severe and scorching fevers: a study of eighteenth-century ship surgeons' journals.</p>

SESSION 6

Fri 6 March 09.00 - 10.45

<p>Session 6A: Language and Knowledge Circulation <i>Nikolaevsky room</i></p> <p><i>Chair:</i> Gijsbert Rutten, Leiden University <i>Session coordinator:</i> Amber Zijlma, Leiden University Libraries</p>	<p>Session 6B: Oceans of Data: New Horizons <i>Max Nettlau room</i></p> <p><i>Chair:</i> Hélder Carvahal, International Institute of Social History <i>Session coordinator:</i> Tara Huveneers, University of Amsterdam</p>	<p>Session 6C: Recentering Histories and Archives <i>Posthumus room</i></p> <p><i>Chair:</i> Filipa Ribeiro da Silva, International Institute of Social History <i>Session coordinator:</i> Jens Aurich, International Institute of Social History</p>
<p>Anna Pytlowany (Independent scholar) - Linguistic Borrowings and Digital Archives: Re-reading Ketelaar's VOC Records.</p> <p>Anjana Aby (Leiden University) - Making Information: The Dutch in Malabar.</p> <p>Philip Post (Utrecht University & Leiden University) - Tracing Intertextual Colonial Legitimacy: The Memoranda of Transfer in the VOC Archives of the Moluccas, 1750–1800.</p> <p>Kay Pepping (Huygens Institute) - How the VOC Wrote Home: Mapping Parallel Information Flows in the OBP Corpus.</p>	<p>André Murteira (New University of Lisbon) - Portuguese Ships lost to Dutch Privateering in Asia: Building a Dataset.</p> <p>Pascal Konings and Britt van Duijvenvoorde (International Institute of Social History & Radboud University Nijmegen) - 'We cannot exist properly without slaves': New Insights into Early Dutch Slave Trade in Asia from ESTA Database, 1621-1660.</p> <p>Brecht Nijman (Huygens Institute & Radboud University Nijmegen) - Testing the Waters: Reconstructing intra-Asian maritime trade networks in the 18th century, a proof of concept.</p> <p>Bethany Warner (International Institute of Social History) - Unlocking European Colonial Archives: Open-Source Approaches to HTR and Colonial Archives.</p>	<p>Leonard Blussé (Leiden University) - Collateral History: The VOC in China and Japan, 1602–1662.</p> <p>Renu Elizabeth Abraham (O.P. Jindal Global University, India) - The Zamorins and the Dutch: A Ritualistic Framework of Engagement.</p> <p>Pouwel Van Schooten (Leiden University) - Forgotten in the Archive, Remembered in Reality: Memories of Slave Descent in 18th century Galle, Sri Lanka.</p> <p>Erik Odegard (International Institute of Social History) - Sing Alap Alap's Soldiers: Madurese Infantry in Company Service, 1761-1768.</p>

WORKSHOPS

GETTING TO KNOW GLOBALISE 1

TRANSCRIPTIONS AND ACCESSING THE ARCHIVES

Tue 3 March 13.15 - 14.15

Tue 3 March 14.30 - 15.30

Wed 4 March 09.00 - 10.00

Nikolaevsky room

In this session, we present the path to the GLOBALISE transcriptions, from scans to searchable text, and demonstrate a number of methods for using the transcriptions, even if you cannot easily read early modern Dutch.

The project utilised the open-source handwritten text recognition tool Loghi to transcribe 5 million scans of the VOC archives. In this session, we first introduce Loghi and the transcription pipeline, followed by a set of tools that are currently under development to help users explore and interpret the resulting texts. These include AI-assisted search, named entity recognition, glossing, and related methods. Together, these approaches make the VOC archives more accessible and interpretable, especially for users with limited knowledge of (early modern) Dutch. Many of these tools will be integrated into the research portal, scheduled for release in the last quarter of 2026.

This session will be partially interactive, giving participants the opportunity to experiment with some of the tools in development for navigating the GLOBALISE collections. Please bring a laptop!

HOST: BETHANY WARNER

Junior Researcher, International Institute of Social History

Bethany Warner is a junior researcher for Colonial Archives and Slavery Studies at the International Institute of Social History, Amsterdam. She is working at the intersection of historical research, archival studies, and digital humanities, with multiple projects related to colonialism and slave trading in Asia, including Voices of Resistance and The Global Business of Slave Trade. Their current work focuses on developing HTR models for Spanish, Portuguese, and French language material, and digital research methods.

HOST: LODEWIJK PETRAM

Project Manager, GLOBALISE

Lodewijk Petram is the project manager of Globalise. He holds a PhD in economic history and is a senior researcher at the Huygens Institute. His publications include *The World's First Stock Exchange* (2014), a financial history with a central role for the VOC. He currently leads a new collaborative project with Erasmus University Rotterdam's School of Economics that uses the Globalise research infrastructure to investigate the long-term impact of early Dutch colonialism in Asia.

GETTING TO KNOW GLOBALISE 2

ANNOTATION AND ENTITY & EVENT RECOGNITION

Tue 3 March 13.15 - 14.15

Tue 3 March 14.30 - 15.30

Wed 4 March 09.00 - 10.00

Souvarine room

This session will present the work performed in Globalise around Entity and Event recognition. As Natural Language Processing tasks, both Entity and Event recognition share methodology, but they differ in the level of linguistic or world knowledge involved in executing them.

We start the session with a general introduction of the ideas behind using Natural Language Processing (NLP) for information extraction within Globalise. We explain how NLP can help turn text into conceptually grouped information. We then focus our attention on Entity and Event recognition specifically, which are types of NLP tasks. We introduce the task design: how were both tasks conceptualized and which method type was chosen for each?

Both tasks rely on annotated data for training models. We will describe the annotation process, from developing guidelines to data curation.

Having a baseline model and gold data is not enough. Model development involves experimenting with many possible settings and parameters against a methodologically-sound setup. We will explain how data splits and experiment tracking are used for different stages of development.

Finally, we go into why the outputs of our models are helpful for historical research by showing some examples of event detection.

HOST: STELLA VERKIJK

PhD candidate, Huygens Institute & VU University Amsterdam

Stella Verkijk is a PhD Candidate at the Huygens Institute and VU Universiteit Amsterdam investigating how to perform Event Reconstruction in the archives of the VOC with language technology. She specializes in domain-specific language modelling.

HOST: SOPHIE ARNOULT

Postdoc researcher, VU University Amsterdam

Sophie Arnoult is a computational linguist and postdoc researcher at the VU Universiteit Amsterdam. She is responsible for Named Entity recognition and disambiguation within Globalise.

GETTING TO KNOW GLOBALISE 3

HISTORICAL DATA AND RESEARCH: PERSONS DATASET

*Tue 3 March 13.15 - 14.15
Scheltema room*

The VOC archives can feel like a sea of words without contextual information about the people mentioned in the records. This session introduces the key concepts behind the GLOBALISE Persons dataset and explores how person-based contextualization can support searching, interpretation, and research in the archive. No technical skills required!

Participants will work with established reference data to identify people in VOC transcriptions and link them to archival texts, thereby reflecting on how new knowledge can be generated from existing data. The session will conclude with a discussion of the challenges of identifying historical persons and a critical reflection on whose lives and experiences remain difficult (or impossible) to research using currently available reference data. Please bring a laptop to fully partake in the session.

HOST: KAY PEPPING

Junior researcher, GLOBALISE

Kay Pepping graduated in history at Leiden, with a focus on early modern diplomacy and colonial history, including a master's thesis on Dutch East India Company (VOC) negotiations at the local level. Now part of the GLOBALISE project at the Huygens Institute, he combines his interests in digital humanities with his interest in the early modern period.

HISTORICAL DATA AND RESEARCH: WEIGHTS & MEASURES DATASET

*Tue 3 March 14.30 - 15.30
Scheltema room*

The VOC archives are only a sea of words if you don't know what you are reading. But what if we can change that by giving users some information about places, people or ships that are written about in the archive? How can this contextual information transform the way in which we comprehend the archive and its contents?

WORKSHOPS

This presentation will focus on an important facet of the project – historical contextualization. It will emphasize on how providing additional information about certain types of entities can be a useful aid for searching and researching the archive. This presentation will specifically introduce datasets on weights and measures and how they interact with the data on commodities and shipping within the GLOBALISE project.

HOST: BRECHT NIJMAN

Junior researcher, GLOBALISE and PhD candidate, Radboud University Nijmegen

Brecht Nijman is Junior Researcher at the Huygens Institute and an external PhD candidate at Radboud University Nijmegen. She has been with the GLOBALISE project since 2022, where she works within the historical contextualization work package. Brecht has been involved in the creation and curation of contextual data for ships, measures, places and polities, as well as the development of the annotation guidelines for named entities. Her PhD research focusses on the development of early modern intra-Asian maritime trade networks. Brecht holds an MA in History from the University of Edinburgh and an MSc in Applied Data Science for Utrecht University.

HISTORICAL DATA AND RESEARCH: PLACES DATASET

*Wed 4 March 09.00 - 10.00
Scheltema room*

The VOC archives are only a sea of words if you don't know what you are reading. But what if we can change that by giving users some information about places, people or ships that are written about in the archive? How can this contextual information transform the way in which we comprehend the archive and its contents?

This presentation will focus on an important facet of the project – historical contextualization. It will emphasize on how providing additional information about certain types of entities can be a useful aid for searching and researching the archive. This presentation will specifically introduce the Places dataset of the GLOBALISE project, discuss its various facets and speak about how and why it was created. The second part of the presentation will comprise a hands-on session. Here, participants will have the opportunity to work closely with the dataset to learn how it can assist them explore and interpret the archive more effectively. Please bring your laptop to the session!

HOST: MANJUSHA KURUPPATH

Team lead Historical Contextualisation, GLOBALISE

Manjusha Kuruppath leads the historical contextualization in the GLOBALISE project. As part of her role, she supervises the creation of datasets of persons, commodities, polities and other entities mentioned in the VOC archives. She has a PhD in history from the University of Leiden and her thesis *Staging Asia* studied the agency of the VOC in transferring information from Asia to Europe in the early modern period. Alongside her work in GLOBALISE, she has worked on two other projects, *Combatting Bias* and *Necessary Reunions: Remarrying Maps to Text and Reconceptualizing Histories of Early Modern Kerala*.

HOST: PHAM THUY DUNG

Junior researcher, GLOBALISE

Pham Thuy Dung obtained an MA History degree from VU University Amsterdam, with a focus on Vietnamese and colonial histories. She currently works as a junior researcher for the GLOBALISE project, where she helps curate datasets on early modern places and ethno-religious groups featuring in the Dutch East India Company archives.

HOST: NIKHIL BELLARYKAR

Independent scholar

Nikhil Bellarykar is an independent researcher who has published in various prominent national and international journals like the *Itinerario*. He specializes in the study of Maratha history and has extensively used the VOC archives to undertake his research. He has participated at prestigious international conferences such as the Maharashtra Studies Conference at Austin, Texas, 2019 and has contributed to the government of Maharashtra's Marathi encyclopedia. Nikhil works with the GLOBALISE project as an external collaborator and is interested in networking and exploring new opportunities for publications and project contributions.

HOST: LEON VAN WISSEN

Research Data Engineer, University of Amsterdam

Leon van Wissen has a background in Dutch literature and computational linguistics and works in the Humanities Labs of the University of Amsterdam. As Data Engineer in Cultural Data Collection and Linking at the UvA's Data Science Centre, he models and publishes data from cultural heritage providers as Linked Open Data and contributes to the development of research infrastructures such as the GLOBALISE project, and the Amsterdam Time Machine (UvA).

OUTSMARTING THE MACHINE

**CRITICALLY EVALUATING
AUTOMATIC DATA
ENRICHMENTS IN TEXT**

Wed 4 March 15.00 - 16.30

Fri 6 March 9.00 - 10.30

Souvarine room

Text annotations made by Machine Learning systems are becoming a widespread aspect of historical research. But how can researchers with no experience or training in Machine Learning judge their output? In this workshop you will learn how.

Labelling entities in a text is an established method of enriching historical sources with language technology. More cutting-edge technology can also label things that happen, such as ships leaving, conflicts being started, relationships changing, and islands being invaded. This is the type of technology we will be focusing on.

The workshop consists of two parts. We start with a short theoretical part, offering an introduction on the inner workings of language technology based on deep neural networks. We then go into the practical part, where we will be evaluating a system's output, analysing a Missive sent from Batavia in 1782 about the English conquering territory in Trinkonomale.

The language of instruction will be English, but to attend this workshop you should be able to read (Early Modern) Dutch and understand the historical context of the archives. You should also bring a laptop.

HOST: STELLA VERKIJK

PhD candidate, Huygens Institute & VU University Amsterdam

Stella Verkijk is a PhD Candidate at the Huygens Institute and VU Universiteit Amsterdam investigating how to perform Event Reconstruction in the archives of the VOC with language technology. She specializes in domain-specific language modelling.

PERFORMANCE LECTURES

DAY 1

Wed 4 March 18.00 - 18.30

Farewell: An Imagined Response to Dutch Colonizers

TogetherTogether: Acero, Cattani & Gaspar

Wednesday, 4 March, 18.00 – 18.30.

Maximum 30 participants due to venue capacity.

Meeting point: Registration desk.

A GLOBALISE team member will lead you to the performance venue.

This performance includes soil. No direct contact occurs but attendees with allergies should use discretion and inform organisers in advance.

This research-based performance departs from the seventeenth-century archives of the Dutch East India Company (VOC). The work is an artistic translation of our research into cultural, spiritual, and epistemic dispossession in the territory now called Indonesia. We depart from the reports of tree extirpations in the Maluku Islands, and on the life of the botanist and merchant Georg Eberhard Rumphius, as an example of the Company's domination attempt of the spice trade, knowledge authorship, and the imposition of violent systems of abduction upon people and territories.

As research-based artists, we are not aiming to solve history, instead, we pose questions about how we perceive and engage with it. How does reproducing archival information enable us to build historical solidarity without re-victimizing and reinforcing colonial narratives? Drawing on Saidiya Hartman's method of critical fabulation, we embody the voices of the soil, the plants, and the sun, disrupting the extractive colonial gaze, and highlighting perspectives of the more-than-human victims of colonial labour regimes. By doing so, we strive to demonstrate how performance can offer alternative modes of engaging with the colonial archive that foreground affect, relationality, and accountability, and expand decolonial methodologies in the humanities and social sciences.

TOGETHERTOGETHER – JULIANA ACERO, STEFANO CATTANI AND RITA GASPAR

TogetherTogether is a research-based artistic collective bringing gatherings, workshops, interventions and performances into both institutional and non-institutional contexts.

Juliana Acero Castellanos is a communication designer, embodied storyteller, and maker with a deep conviction for social design. Her practice explores narratives as spaces for emotional and political reflection.

Stefano Cattani is a research-based visual and performance artist. His work, rooted in queerness, investigates the intersection of body, identity and space.

Rita Gaspar is a designer, storyteller, and activist. Her work explores resistance, collectivity, and borders through writing, movement, disruptive gestures and intimate spaces.

»Mother-of-Oil« Colonial roots of the oil company Shell in Indonesia.

Carmen Draxler

Thursday, 5 March

- Session 1: 12.30 – 13.00
- Session 2: 13.30 – 14.00 (in parallel to Panel Session 4)
- Session 3: 14.30 – 15.00

These are repeat sessions.

Maximum 10 participants each session due to venue capacity.

Meeting point: Registration desk.

A GLOBALISE team member will lead you to the performance venue.

This performance takes place in a darkened, enclosed space.

Please use discretion if you are sensitive to such environments.

»**Mother-of-Oil**« is an archival research project that traces the colonial roots of the Dutch-British oil company Shell in Indonesia. By following the stories of seashells from the Indo-Pacific, the research unfolds as a relational map of archival material that reveals Shell's entanglement with the Dutch East India Company (VOC).

Like tulips, seashells were highly coveted commodities in the 17th century that captivated many wealthy Europeans and became a symbol of power and prestige – a symbol that is the distinctive trademark of the global oil empire today. Before extracting oil, Shell's predecessors sold trinket boxes adorned with seashells from the Indo-Pacific Ocean.

Through layering visual evidence from the collections of the National Archive, the Shell Historical Heritage Archive, and the Rijksmuseum, a counternarrative that disrupts the company's official account becomes evident. Presented as lecture performance, the story highlights how the commodification of marine life through colonial practices became a template for fossil capitalism, and emphasizes the urgency to recognize that decarbonisation requires challenging colonial continuities as seashells are important to mitigate climate change.

AN UNNATURAL HISTORY, A Performance Lecture. *Fugitive Desire under VOC Capitalist Erasure, made legible with Artistic Research methods by excavating the Sodomy Criminal Case records in the Colonial VOC Archive, Cape Town, 1652-1795.*

Roelof Petrus van Wyk

Thursday, 4 March, 12.30 - 13.00

Location: Posthumus room

An Unnatural History is a performance lecture that excavates fugitive same-sex desire from the sodomy trial records of the Dutch East India Company (VOC) archive at the Cape of Good Hope (1652–1795). Drawing on over 200 criminal case files, the work engages archival fragments produced through surveillance, interrogation, and punishment, reading them not only as instruments of colonial control but as inadvertent repositories of affective and social bonds. These records, intended to erase, paradoxically preserve traces of a same-sex subculture operating within the interstices of early modern colonial capitalism.

Positioned as a queer artistic researcher and thirteenth-generation descendant of Dutch settlers, Roelof approaches the VOC archive as a haunted site, engaging in an embodied practice of voicing queer ancestral kin. Through poetic text, sound, and visual composition, the performance translates across languages and registers, activating the non-linear temporality of queer life through fragments of testimony and witness.

Artistic research functions here as a critical method that reanimates spectral intimacies and enables speculative reconstructions of social worlds the colonial courts sought to obliterate. By shifting homosocial traces in legal records toward the homoerotic, the work queers the colonial narrative and opens affective circuits between past and present. This approach lays the groundwork for a broader thesis on capitalism's contradictory role in both producing and suppressing same-sex cultures of desire, contributing to an understanding of queer counterpublic formation within colonial modernity.

Roelof Petrus van Wyk is a queer South African artist, architect, researcher, and curator whose interdisciplinary practice explores the entanglements of visual culture, archives, desire, and power. Trained in architecture and visual culture (Goldsmiths/ London), with a PhD in Curatorial, Public and Visual Cultures (WITS/Johannesburg), his work spans photography, performance, sound, installation, and artistic research methodologies. Engaging colonial and modern archives as sensorial, affective fields, he develops counter-histories that foreground repressed and marginalised narratives, particularly around sexuality and capitalism. Van Wyk has exhibited and performed internationally, curated major platforms including the Johannesburg Pavilion at the Venice Biennale, and is currently an Artistic Research Fellow at Stellenbosch University, where he investigates queer counter publics and archival memory.

AN

UNNATURAL HISTORIÆ

BY

ROELOF PETRUS VAN WYK

RIZKY KALEBOS

Rizky Kalebos (1995) is a city planner from the Netherlands with roots in Indonesia, who researches the legacy of colonialism in both the Netherlands and Indonesia in cities, architecture, language and food. In Amsterdam and Den Haag he organizes walking tours through the city centers showing buildings, sculptures and artworks connected to Indonesia and how the country shaped these cities.

WALKING TOUR

DAY 0

Tue 3 March, 15.30 - 17.00

DUTCH EAST INDIA COMPANY IN AMSTERDAM WALK

Rizky Kalebos

Tue 3 March, 15.30 – 17.00

Duration: 1.5 hours

Distance to walk: about 4.5 km.

Meeting point: IISG main entrance.

In this walk through the former harbour of Amsterdam, Rizky will elaborate on the history of the area and the legacy of colonialism on the urban fabric of the city. Even though the remnants of the former shipping wharf of the Dutch East India Company are few, the size or the area is still significant of the city center. By looking through a geographical lens, the walk explores how global trade has shaped the city.

The walk will start from the conference location, continuing through the former VOC wharf, along locations that reflect on the past such as the replica VOC ship, Scheepvaarthuis and Schreierstoren. These landmarks from different periods show how imagery around the VOC has developed and is still being shaped. The walk will end at the former headquarters of the VOC, now the UvA.

ABSTRACTS OF PAPERS

SESSION 1A

MATERIAL CULTURE
AND SOCIAL LIFEWed 4 March 10.30 - 12.00
Nikolaevsky room

Chair: Tristan Mostert, Leiden University
Session coordinator: Nur'Ain Taha, Utrecht University

UNBOXING THE VOC ARCHIVES: ON THE MATERIAL CULTURE OF BETEL CHEWING

The digitisation of VOC archives reveals a wealth of relevant information that allow historical investigations of life in early Dutch colonial society to focus on the intimacies between people and things. Only a fraction of everyday and luxury items from seventeenth-century European households in Asia has been preserved, and what has been handed down is often difficult for researchers to access. As such, despite the now widely held view among historians that “things talk”, written records remain indispensable for reconstructing the contexts in which those things were produced, used, exchanged, and attributed meaning.

This paper takes my ongoing study of the role of betel boxes and the associated practice of betel chewing under Company servants in Asia as an example of how object-centred research benefits from the new digital historical methods that are central to the GLOBALISE project. It thus has a dual purpose. Firstly, it offers some reflections, based on my own research, on the opportunities and constraints of the digitised VOC archives and related digital methods. The second purpose of this paper is to share some preliminary findings regarding the possession and use of betel boxes in the context of the VOC in the seventeenth century.

JOSEPHINE KOOPMAN

European University Institute, Florence

Josephine Koopman is a PhD candidate in History at the European University Institute. Her dissertation project, ‘The World in a Box: Snuff Tobacco in the Global Dutch Republic’, concerns material cultures of intoxication in the early modern Dutch world. She is currently working on a chapter about the use of betel and betel boxes among Europeans in late seventeenth and early eighteenth-century South and Southeast Asia. In 2023-2024 she was the Johan Huizinga Research Fellow at the Rijksmuseum.

COLLECTING SHELLS AT A COST: JOHAN NIEUHOF'S ACCOUNT OF THE PEARL AND CHANK SHELL FISHERY AT TOOTHUKUDI, 1664-1665

This paper examines Johan Nieuhof's account of the pearl fishery at Toothukudi between 1664 and 1665, a VOC post on the southeastern coast of India. Through an examination of this account, published in *Gedenkwaerdige Zee en Lantreize* [...] (1682), this paper considers how Nieuhof's detailed description of the pearl fishery reveals its human cost. This paper frames this account in its historical context through a comparative analysis of extant VOC reports from Toothukudi (greatly aided by the GLOBALISE transcription viewer) and other accounts of this posting in the mid-17th century, such as by Wouter Schouten. This analysis highlights the impoverishment and risks endured by the divers, mostly from the coastal Parava community, on whom this industry depended. Additionally, Nieuhof's observations reflect his self-identification as a *liefhebber van rariteyten*, evidencing how VOC trade and privateering facilitated the movement of natural specimens and curiosities—in particular pearl-oyster and chank shells—into Dutch and European collections. While much scholarly attention has focused on Nieuhof's earlier, well known account of mainland China, this paper positions *Zee en Lantreize* as an understudied and valuable source for understanding the intersections between the expanding global trade network of the VOC, and the culture of collecting shells and rarities in the early modern Dutch Republic, reflecting ultimately on their human cost.

ISABELLE STONE

The Open University and The Museum of the Home, London

Isabelle Stone is a current PhD student with The Open University and The Museum of the Home (London) working on the project *Netherlandish networks: Home-making in an age of emerging global capitalism (1565-1799)*. She recently completed her research master's in art history at Utrecht University, graduating cum laude. She received her bachelor's degree in Art History and Visual Culture' from the University of Exeter. Her research interests stem from a fascination with the visual and material cultural exchange between the Dutch Republic, Britain and their expanding global trade and colonial networks in the early modern period.

AN ATTEMPT TO CHARACTERIZE THE SOCIAL AND CULTURAL IDENTITY OF THE VOC CENTERS IN SRI LANKA IN THE 18TH CENTURY

This paper follows on from previous publications of the presenter which have addressed the Dutch character of the VOC settlement in Sri Lanka/Ceylon. These studies focused primarily on the walled port town of Galle, some 112 km south of Colombo. Research in documents kept at the National Archives of Sri Lanka and Indonesia yielded interesting details about material aspects of a certain "Dutch" identity—some objects, such as the waffle iron and the poffertjes pan, which this study labels "index fossils," which as insignia of Dutchness simply demonstrated that character. This paper has two goals. First, it is necessary to see whether these "index fossils" and similar objects of material culture also appeared in documents from other VOC settlements. The tools of the Globalise project would prove to be a valuable resource in this regard, and the question could easily be confirmed. Secondly, it is important to describe in a short way, using information from the data-rich web, what remains in Sri Lanka can be seen of the periods of colonial presence of Portugal, the Netherlands and England respectively, and in doing so try to answer the question why so little remains of the Dutch Period (1638-1796) are left.

LODEWIJK J. WAGENAAR

Independent scholar (formerly University of Amsterdam)

Lodewijk Wagenaar has been a Lecturer in History at the University of Amsterdam (UvA), The Netherlands, and a curator of the Amsterdam Museum. Since 1980 he has been involved in museum and education projects in Colombo, Sri Lanka, followed by museum projects in Jakarta, Indonesia, since 1990. He has published widely on the early modern history of Sri Lanka, including 'The Dutch East India Company (VOC) and its use of Company slaves (Compagnies lijfeijgenen) in Sri Lanka around 1681', in: D.D. da Silva, H. Hägerdal, A. Kalashnikova and F. Ribeiro da Silva, *Colonial Encounters and Slavery in Early Modern Asia*. Leiden University Press 2025.

SESSION 1B

MOBILITIES

Wed 4 March 10.30 - 12.00
Max Nettleau room

Chair: Marieke Hendriksen, Huygens Institute
Session coordinator: Bente de Leede, Leiden University

THE NUSANTARA HAJJ PILGRIMAGE IN THE 17TH AND 18TH CENTURIES: THE EMERGENCE OF A GLOBAL UMMAH IDENTITY

The Hajj pilgrimage was not only a personal religious obligation for pre-modern Indonesian Muslims. It was a multifaceted phenomenon with significant political and social dimensions. These dimensions arose from the pilgrimage's nature as a trans-local journey that connected Muslims from the archipelago with their counterparts across the Indian Ocean world. These meetings fostered a sense of a shared ummah (a global Muslim community) that transcended local, ethnic, and political boundaries. This research will analyze how pilgrimages facilitated meetings and exchanges of ideas between Muslims in the archipelago and those from various parts of the world. By analyzing the archives of the Dutch East India Company (VOC), Overgekomen Breiven en Papieren (OBP), this research will also contribute to the development of a resilient political-religious identity that is opposed to VOC influence and support the formation of a global Ummah identity. By using the VOC archives to uncover a history that existed beyond the company's purview, this study reveals that the Hajj was not just a religious journey but a political act and offers an example of how a decentered approach can reveal new and inclusive histories of Muslim societies and their resilience in the face of colonial encroachment.

RONI TABRONI

Research Center for Treasures of Religion and Civilization, National Research and Innovation Agency (BRIN), Indonesia

Roni Tabroni is a Junior Researcher at the Research Center for Treasures of Religion and Civilization, National Research and Innovation Agency (BRIN), Indonesia. Roni researches Indonesian Islamic history, particularly the history of political Islam and has authored several articles, such as the contribution of local knowledge in the expansion of the Sultanate of Banten on the spice route of the Nusantara (2023), The transformation of the Salafism movement in Indonesia (2023), Mapping Islam: New Order Policy, Mosque Distribution, and Religious Dynamics In West Java, Indonesia (2024), and A Historical Analysis Of Chinese Muslim Citizenship In The New Order Era Indonesia (2025).

MARATHA OVERSEAS TRADE IN THE 17TH CENTURY- TRACING THE SHIP SHAMBHU PRASAD THROUGH THE VOC ARCHIVES.

The Marathas arose as a strong regional power in western Deccan in the 2nd half of the 17th century CE, against powerful enemies like the Adil Shahis and the Mughals. Shivaji, the founder of Maratha polity, is known to have created a full-time navy and also built a number of coastal fortifications. What is less well known, however, is the existence of the Maratha merchant marine and its activities in 17th century.

In Maratha historiography, overseas trade occupies a largely peripheral position, owing no doubt to extremely scanty references thereof. With the discovery of three voyages of the Maratha ship Shambhu Prasad, this lacuna is filled to a large extent. The VOC records mention attributes such as cargo, tonnage, taxation rates, etc. in great detail. The surrounding political and economic discussions add rich layers to the narrative and help reconstruct the 17th century overseas Maratha trade with the complexities thereof.

Enabled by these findings, this paper traces the Shambhu Prasad through the VOC records, and contextualizes of the various aspects of its journey with an appropriate background and framework. This will help recreate the modalities of Maratha overseas trade and its place within the Indian ocean trade.

NIKHIL BELLARYKAR

Independent scholar

Nikhil Bellarykar is an independent researcher who has published in various prominent national and international journals like the *Itinerario*. He specializes in the study of Maratha history and has extensively used the VOC archives to undertake his research. He has participated at prestigious international conferences such as the Maharashtra Studies Conference at Austin, Texas, 2019 and has contributed to the government of Maharashtra's Marathi encyclopedia. Nikhil works with the GLOBALISE project as an external collaborator and is interested in networking and exploring new opportunities for publications and project contributions.

GLOBALISE AND UNLOCKED FOOD ARCHIVES

The study of Indonesia's culinary history traditionally centers on two key periods: the premodern era, informed by archaeological findings and classical texts, and the late-colonial period, captured in printed records. Building on Globalise material, Tom Hoogervorst reconstructs elements of Indonesia's premodern foodways from the period in between. The *ingekomen brieven* underscore a range of ingredients and dishes that remain integral to Indonesia and its broader cultural spheres, alongside food items from China, South Asia, and

Europe. The material can and should be explored for its daily menus, inventory lists, and casual descriptions of food, details that would be difficult to locate without digital search tools. The Globalise infrastructure makes it possible to highlight culinary transformations during this pivotal period, including the introduction of soy products from East Asia, foodstuffs from the Americas, and European practices that gradually gained wider acceptance. Tom Hoogervorst also address the limitations and gaps in the material, arguing that the newly accessible sources are nevertheless invaluable for advancing our understanding of the region's culinary history when approached critically. Ideally, the food-related Globalise material should be cross-referenced with the works of Rumphius, as well as with Malay and Javanese sources from the same or slightly later periods.

TOM HOOGERVORST

KITLV

Tom Hoogervorst is a senior researcher at the Royal Netherlands Institute of Southeast Asian and Caribbean Studies (KITLV) and adjunct professor at Universitas Negeri Malang. His interest in culinary history grew out of his research on Malay and Javanese language history, which revealed lesser-known episodes of cultural contact. He has examined Indonesia's foodscapes using primary sources in local languages, from Old Javanese court poetry to colonial-era vernacular Malay publications. His current research traces the culinary trajectories of Indonesian-descended diasporas in Suriname, Sri Lanka, and South Africa, with the aim of mapping the forces and mechanisms that drive culinary change.

SESSION 1C

**DIGITAL HUMANITIES APPROACHES
TO THE VOC ARCHIVE**Wed 4 March 10.30 - 12.00
Posthumus room

Chair: Stella Verkijk, Huygens Institute & VU University Amsterdam
Session coordinator: Bethany Warner, International Institute of Social History

**TRACING HISTORICAL TORTOISESHELL EXPLOITATION AND
TRADE THROUGH AI-DRIVEN ANALYSIS**

The Dutch East India Company (VOC) played a central role in early modern global trade, yet the ecological consequences of its commerce remain poorly quantified. This pilot study investigates the trade in tortoiseshell, derived from the critically endangered hawksbill turtle (*Eretmochelys imbricata*), through the digitised Overgekomen Brieven en Papieren (OBP) series made available via the GLOBALISE project. Using AI-assisted archival analysis, we develop a computational pipeline to identify, verify, and extract references to tortoiseshell across the OBP corpus. By combining expanded keyword searches, fuzzy matching, contextual evaluation with Large Language Models (LLMs), we aim to reconstruct the temporal and spatial dimensions of VOC tortoiseshell trade. Although quantitative reconstruction is ongoing, this study demonstrates how colonial archives can be transformed into ecological datasets. More broadly, it reframes VOC trade not only as a commercial enterprise but as a historical process of large-scale biological extraction, illustrating how AI-assisted reading can contribute to environmental history and the study of long-term biodiversity loss.

WILLEMEN DE KOCK

University of Groningen

Dr. Willemien de Kock is a marine ecologist who uses historical and archaeological sources to reconstruct past ecosystems. Her research focuses on long-term anthropogenic impacts and comparisons between ancient and modern marine and freshwater environments. Using historical ecology methods such as stable isotope analysis, molecular tools, and archival research, she investigates past species' habitat use, diets, and patterns of animal exploitation to define environmental baselines, and explore resilience and change in human-ecosystem relationships.

EMIN TATAR

University of Groningen

Dr. Emin Tatar is a data scientist with a PhD in mathematics working at the Center

for Information Technology at the University of Groningen. His work is highly interdisciplinary, supporting research across domains through advanced data analysis and computational methods. With expertise in machine learning and large language models, he focuses on developing and applying scalable, data-driven solutions to complex research questions.

ROB LENDERS

Radboud University Nijmegen

Dr. Rob Lenders is a researcher in historical ecology at Radboud University Nijmegen. He focuses on human-animal relationships during the Holocene in north-western Europe, with a particular emphasis on the period from Roman times to the early modern period. He investigates how humans have influenced animal populations, but also what impact animals have had on human behaviour. For his research, he uses both archaeological data and written sources. The animal groups he focuses on are mammals, fish, amphibians and reptiles.

AGGREGATING THE FAIR ASSESSMENT RESULTS OF DATASETS BY THE GLOBALISE COMMUNITY FOR EVALUATING FAIR DATA MANAGEMENT

GLOBALISE is a collaborative initiative involving the Huygens Institute and a few other Dutch institutions. Much of the research in the GLOBALISE community is data-centric, taking advantage a range of digital methods. The datasets range from raw historical data (e.g., slavery trade records) to machine-actionable transcriptions, often enhanced and semantically annotated using the GLOBALISE Thesaurus. Researchers apply the FAIR principles (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability) at varying levels in their data management, documented in their FAIR Implementation Profiles (FIPs). To automate FAIR assessments, tools like F-UJI and FAIR Checker have been developed. This work extends a framework by aggregating FAIRness assessment results from multiple tools, enabling analysis of the community's data management practices. We also compare these aggregated results with the GLOBALISE FIP to identify gaps and limitations. The Zenodo datasets performed well with both the Naive and Rigid methods across all sub-principles.

SHUAI WANG

Utrecht University

Shuai Wang has been working as a software steward at Maastricht University since March 2025 while remaining a guest researcher at VU Amsterdam. In the past, Shuai has worked as a scientific engineer at the FAIR Expertise Hub where Shuai promoted FAIR principles and FAIR Implementation in communities in social sciences and humanities in the Netherlands.

ANDRE VALDESTILHAS

VU University Amsterdam

Andre Valdestilhas is a highly motivated and results-oriented computer science researcher with over 20 years of experience. Andre is skilled in applying semantic web technologies and large language models to materials science, social sciences, and the humanities. With a proven track record in research leadership and publication, Andre also has extensive experience in conference organization and participation as a chair, program committee member, and reviewer for top venues like ICWI, ESWC, ISWC, and The Semantic Web Journal.

RONALD SIEBES

VU University Amsterdam

Ronald Siebes is a senior researcher at the User Centric Data Science group in the department Computer Science at the VU Amsterdam. He applies Linked Data research and Machine Learning in various national and European projects, ranging from Social Sciences, Humanities to IoT. Ronald received his Ph.D. in Artificial Intelligence where he worked on distributed reasoning algorithms using Peer-to-Peer technology.

ANGELICA MAINERI

ODISSEI

Angelica Maineri is the Data Manager at the Dutch research infrastructure for the social sciences ODISSEI, where she oversees work with FAIR implementation to make data available securely through the infrastructure. She holds a PhD in Sociology from Tilburg University, and is passionate about Open Science.

SESSION 2A

THE DUTCH REFORMED
CHURCH AND COLONIALISMWed 4 March 15.00 - 16.30
Nikolaevsky room

Chair: Dienke Hondius, VU University Amsterdam
Session coordinator: Bente de Leede, Leiden University

**THE DUTCH REFORMED CHURCH ON AMBON (1605-1700):
CREATING POWER STRUCTURES AND FRAMING THE OTHER**

This paper investigates how the experiences of the first ministers of the Dutch Reformed Church (DRC) mission in the 17th-century Ambon, following the colonization efforts of the Dutch East India Company (VOC), shaped perspectives of the indigenous people in the Dutch Republic. The paper takes a post-colonial perspective to critique existing Eurocentric historiography that often overlooks the negative framing of the colonized "other." The paper argues that despite the DRC's anti-Catholic stance, its mission framework mirrored the "civilization versus barbarism" divide established in the Catholic Valladolid debate (1550-1551). The DRC ministers' frustration with the failure of their rigid conversion methods (based on Synod of Dordt dogmas) led to increased calls for the use of force and a consistently negative portrayal of the Ambonese indigenous people as "weak, treacherous barbarians" in reports sent back to the Dutch Republic. Sebastiaen Danckaerts's pamphlet from 1621, *Historisch ende Grondich Verhael van den standt des Christendoms int quartier van Ambonia*, is identified as a key primary source that widely distributed this negative frame. The paper shows that Danckaerts's 17th-century image of the indigenous person was consistently quoted and referred to in the following centuries, leaving a lasting frame of "the other" till the present date.

JON KUIPER

University of Groningen

Jon Kuiper is a Master student in the History Department of the University of Groningen. His research is focused on the development of Calvinist ideology in the Dutch Reformed Church in the 17th century and the impact this ideology had on the identity of the Dutch Republic.

THE VOC, THE CHURCH, AND THE MASSACRE OF BANDA IN 1621

Europeans came to Banda to take nutmeg and mace to be sold in Europe for exorbitantly high prices. In 1602 the VOC was established to gain monopoly of spice trading in the East Indies. In

1621 Jan Pieterszoon Coen, the Governor General of the VOC, led the troops to defeat Banda. His attack that led into the massacre of thousands of the native inhabitants and enslavement of so many of the survivors had been notoriously known. Coen was also well known as a strong Calvinist. By the time Coen defeated Banda, the Dutch Reformed church had started to grow in the region. However, the church was largely silent on the attack. This paper focuses on the complex relationships between the VOC and the Dutch Reformed church in the East Indies. The main aim of this paper is to show that the church was unable to raise its voice against the cruelty of the VOC because it worked under the authority of the VOC. The ministers were the employees of the VOC. The church did not have the ability to criticize the Company, and therefore it failed to apply the core theological teaching of Christianity to love God and to love their neighbors as themselves.

YUDHA THianto

Calvin Theological Seminary, USA

Yudha Thianto is P. J. Zondervan Chair and Professor of History of Christianity and Reformed Theology at Calvin Theological Seminary. His research focuses on the history of the Dutch Reformed Church in the East Indies at the time of the VOC. His most recent publications include, *The Way to Heaven: Catechisms and Sermons in the Establishment of the Dutch Reformed Church in the East Indies* (Wipf & Stock, 2014), *An Explorer's Guide to John Calvin* (IVP Academic, 2022), *The Old Testament, Calvin, and the Reformed Tradition*, ed., (Brill, June 2024), and "Singing in Opposition: The Metrical Psalms in Reformed and Anabaptist Churches in the Netherlands in the Seventeenth Century," in *Calvin Theological Journal* 59.2 (2024).

A NEW BIOGRAPHICAL DICTIONARY OF NETHERLANDS INDIAN MINISTERS, SICK-COMFORTERS AND MISSIONARIES 1600-1960

The biographical dictionaries of VOC church workers, compiled by C.A.L. van Troostenburg de Bruijn in 1893/1902, are among the most cited reference works in the historiography of the Netherlands Indies. Both 'predikanten' serving in the archipelago and 'krankenbezoekers' or 'ziekentroosters' sailing at the company ships were listed by him in alphabetical-lexicographical order. Unfortunately, partly due the author's blindness, the documentation of the major clergy was inaccurate already at publication, while the coverage of the minor clergy was not more than a quarter of all laymen who must have been employed over two centuries. Although a lot of additional information has been made available in the meantime, a systematic investigation using not only the VOC (and WIC) sources, but the very fragmentary church archives too, has not been presented yet. The Digital Dutch Religious History project (DigiDuRe) at Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam is developing a database including all ministers and lay pastors examined by the public church and sent out to overseas locations between 1600 and 1800. The GLOBALISE infrastructure offers many possibilities for enriching and connecting the data of persons, places, careers, and other entities. My paper will explain the datamodel and its sources, considering new research challenges in Dutch religious and colonial history.

FRED VAN LIEBURG

VU University Amsterdam

Fred van Lieburg is professor of religious history in the Faculty of Social Sciences and Humanities at VU Universiteit Amsterdam, director of the HDC Centre for Religious History, and guest professor for Dutch church history at Protestantse Theologische Universiteit Utrecht. His large range of research and publications includes an often quoted article in Gerrit Schutte's volume 'Het Indisch Sion' (2002), offering a quantitative approach off the church workers of the VOC in the 17th and 18th centuries.

SESSION 2B

TRADE, COLONIAL EXPANSION AND GLOCAL NETWORKS

Wed 4 March 15.00 - 16.30
Max Nettle room

Chair: Erik Odegard, International Institute of Social History
Session coordinator: Britt van Duijvenvoorde, International Institute of Social History

BETWEEN THE CARTAZ AND THE ZEEBRIEF: THE ZAMORIN'S MARITIME DIPLOMACY, 1633-1766

In Indian Ocean historiography, Vasco da Gama's arrival at Calicut and the early encounters between the Portuguese Estado da Índia and the Zamorin of Calicut are often treated as formative moments. This narrative, however, usually ends in 1663 with the Portuguese expulsion from Malabar by the Dutch East India Company (VOC). This study, however, examines the post-1663 relationship between the Zamorin and the Portuguese and its ongoing influence on Calicut's maritime world. In the immediate aftermath of their defeat, the Portuguese were compelled to commercially engage with the Mappila merchants, despite earlier hostilities, largely in response to the shared threat posed by the VOC. This fragile collaboration encouraged the growth of alternative ports such as Tanur but repeatedly fractured as the Portuguese sought to reassert maritime authority through naval coercion and the enforcement of the Cartaz system. Their renewed attempt to regain access to Calicut culminated in 1682 after prolonged negotiations with the Zamorin.

Framed within Sanjay Subrahmanyam's concept of the "Age of Contained Conflicts," the study demonstrates how the Zamorin skilfully balanced Portuguese and Dutch claims to maritime control, mediated through competing pass systems, such as the Cartaz and Zeebrief. By containing disputes, promoting coastal markets, negotiating concessions, and preserving space for Mappila and other local merchants, the Zamorin maintained a flexible and resilient commercial order within overlapping legal regimes.

AJAY JOY MATHEW

Mahatma Gandhi University, Kerala, India

Ajay Joy Mathew is a PhD research scholar in the Department of History at Union Christian College, Aluva. He completed his Master's degree in History from the School of Social Sciences, Mahatma Gandhi University, Kerala. His research interests include Indian Ocean trade, slavery, and the economic and agrarian developments of eighteenth-century Kerala. He is particularly interested in the role of the Dutch East India Company (VOC) and its commercial, financial, and political engagements on the

Malabar Coast. Currently in the first year of his PhD programme, his research draws on Dutch archival sources to examine questions of debt, credit, land, and labour, and to explore the interactions between colonial enterprises and local societies within the broader context of early modern Indian Ocean history.

THE MAKING OF COLOMBO: DUTCH AND LANKAN ENGINEERING, INFRASTRUCTURES AND COMMODITY TRADE, 1745-1795

This paper discusses a history of several ecosystem engineering projects in and around Colombo and its suburbs in the eighteenth century, to trace how both colonial and indigenous hydrological structures cumulatively rose this Global South hub from the Kelani estuary. It argues that its vicinity to the historical Kottean kingdom and the Kelani river, which formed a gateway to the agriculturally productive hinterlands, pushed people to create a port city in a place that was in reality poorly suited for it. Fighting against sediment, water, and wildlife, both localised and colonial polities attempted to design and maintain Colombo as a hub in the Indian Ocean World network in what – crucially – is one of the busiest continuous sea routes in world history. To accomplish this, they relied on labour, knowledge, and material that originated from both local, and global sources. Readyng the city for the extraction of commodities – a process which both colonial authorities and Lankan planters and traders benefited from – permanently impacted the social and ecological environments of the historical Kalanpu region. The challenge lies, however, in reconstructing the lived experience of the labourers and small-scale landowners whose lives, arguably, were most deeply impacted by the process that was to accommodate Colombo for the extraction of resources.

LUC BULTEN

Radboud University Nijmegen

Luc Bulten is a postdoctoral fellow in Sri Lankan History at the University of Cambridge, and affiliated with Queens' college as postdoctoral research associate. He also holds a position at Radboud University in Nijmegen as an assistant professor of social and economic history. In his work, Luc is especially interested in local-colonial interactions in South and Southeast Asia related to labour regimes, land tenure, family history, tax farming, intra-Asian trade, the environment and the reciprocal production of knowledge and institutions.

EXPLORING GLOBAL TEXTILE CIRCULATION WITH THE DUTCH TEXTILE TRADE PROJECT

The Dutch Textile Trade Project (co-led with Carrie Anderson) draws on the extensive documentation of Dutch global trade companies (VOC, WIC, MCC) to better understand the global circulation of textiles in the seventeenth and eighteenth centuries. We consider the data of this trade alongside material and visual evidence of traded textiles, drawing on the methods of art history, economics, material culture, and digital humanities. Our intention is to generate further questions about this trade through exploration of the data and data visualization tools on our project website.

Data is, as we all know, not neutral, and requires careful interpretation. In this project, we're drawing data from company records, companies whose purpose was to exploit people and landscapes and which created conditions which persist to this day. We thus aim to work against the documents and their legacy, to seek evidence of patterns of consumption in places across the world where the Dutch recorded just their own view, in order to understand how these records can illuminate non-Dutch perspectives. In this presentation, I'll explore a case study to show both the possibilities and limits of distant reading methods and tools.

MARSELY KEHOE

Independent Scholar

Marsely Kehoe is an independent scholar based in Michigan, USA. She earned her PhD in Art History in 2012 from the University of Wisconsin and is the author of *Trade, Globalization, and Dutch Art and Architecture* (2023, Amsterdam University Press), and articles on city planning and architecture in Dutch colonial cities, nautilus cups, and digital humanities, as well as co-leader of the Dutch Textile Trade Project.

SESSION 2C

CURRENCIES, POLITICS
AND LABOURWed 4 March 15.00 - 16.30
Posthumus room*Chair: Maarten Manse, Linnaeus University**Session coordinator: Vany Susanto, University of Amsterdam***"DUIT" AND ARABIC SCRIPTS IN COINS PRODUCED BY THE DUTCH DURING THE COLONIAL PERIOD IN INDONESIA**

The history of the colonisation of the VOC–Dutch East India Company left both intangible and tangible heritage, one of which is the word “duit.” This word is found not only in Latin script and the Dutch language but also in Arabic script. In addition, there are coins bearing Arabic language and Arabic script using the term “dirham,” minted in the eighteenth and nineteenth centuries.

This preliminary study refers to the Italian historian Carlo Ginzburg’s concept of microhistory, a genre that focuses on small units of research. Accordingly, a microhistorical approach is applied through research on origins, interpreted here as the history of objects, including data from the GLOBALISE project.

Based on observations of coins as artefacts in a museum as well as digital photographs, this study identifies three variations of Arabic-script inscriptions on VOC–Dutch East India coins: (a) دويت جاو (duit Jawa) (b) درهم من كمفن ولندوي /dirham min kumpani walandawi (“Dirham of the Holland Company”) without the article ال (al)- (definite article) in the words “kumpani” and “walandawi”, with the reverse reading جزيرة جاوالكبير ا لى / ila Jazirati Jawa al-Kabir) (“to Island of Great Java”) ; and (c) درهم من الكمفن الولندوي (dirham min al-kumpani al-walandawi with the article ال (al)- in both words, also with the reverse inscription ا لى جزيرة جاوالكبير (ila Jazirati Jawa al-Kabir).

NURMAN KHOLIS

The Research Centre for Treasures of Religion and Civilization, Research Organization for Archaeology, Language, and Literature, National Research and Innovation Agency (BRIN), Indonesia

Nurman Kholis is a Researcher of the Research Centre for Treasures of Religion and Civilization, Research Organization for Archaeology, Language, and Literature, National Research and Innovation Agency (BRIN), Indonesia. He is a graduate from German Language Study Program D3 (1998), Communication Science Program S1 (2001), Philo-

logy on Pegon (Arabic Scripts in Sundanese) in Magister (2010) and Philology on Jawi (Arabic Scripts in Malay) in Doctoral Program (2018), all of which were conducted at Padjadjaran University, Bandung. He also participated a Short Course at Goethe Universität Frankfurt (December 2014) and benchmarking on religious heritage management to Hamburg Universität (May 2018).

THE TRAVAILS OF PAPER CURRENCY IN THE DUTCH INDIAN OCEAN, 1780-1825

This article examines the efforts of local agents of the Dutch East India Company (Vereenigde Oostindische Compagnie, VOC) to introduce paper currency in three settings: Cape Colony, Ceylon, and Batavia. Rather than being a decision handed on down by authorities in the Dutch Republic, this was an initiative of local VOC employees. As we argue, this was a response to a conjunctural liquidity crisis – real or imagined - confronting not only the company and its settlements in the Indian Ocean, but European overseas enterprise the world over. Although paper currency was seen as a temporary fix by VOC agents, the medium long outlasted the company's collapse in 1799, surviving in some cases for another half century or more.

MAARTEN DRAPER

European University Institute, Florence

Maarten Draper is a Research Fellow on the ERC-funded project 'CAPASIA: The Asian Origins of Global Capitalism' at the European University Institute (EUI) in Florence. He is a socio-economic historian of the early modern period with particular interests in the history of commerce, finance, and shipping. His research concerns how informal networks, migration, and institutions interact and shape economic and commercial behaviour in this period. He was previously a lecturer at the University of Groningen and completed his PhD at the EUI.

THE DEEP MONETIZATION OF INDIA AND CHANGING LABOUR RELATIONS 1500-1900

This paper is a compilation of abstracts from my recent book *Money of the Masses. Copper Coin Production and Circulation in India 1500-1900* (New Delhi: Manohar, 2026). Its main argument, using deep monetization as a guide fossil, is that From the sixteenth century onwards India has been as deeply monetized as Europe and China. This implies the presence of an active labour market, much more important than in contemporaneous Russia and North America. There are also important differences with early-modern and modern Western Europe because of the caste system and the existence of unpaid and unfree labour in India.

JAN LUCASSEN

International Institute of Social History

Jan Lucassen studied history at Leiden University and obtained his PhD at Utrecht University in 1984 with *Migrant Labour in Europe 1600-1900. The Drift to the North Sea* (London, 1987). He specializes in the history of labour, the long-term development of labour relations, migration and monetisation in relation to the development of wage labour. From 1990 until his retirement in 2012, he was Professor of International and Comparative Social History at the VU Universiteit Amsterdam. His publications include *The Story of Work: A New History of Humanity* (New Haven, 2021), and *Money of the Masses. Coin production and circulation in India*, ed. (New Delhi, 2025).

SESSION 3A

**MEDIATORS, KNOWLEDGE
AND CONTESTATION**Thu 5 March 09.00 - 10.40
Nikolaevsky room

Chair: Jos Gommans, Leiden University
Session coordinator: Muhammad Asyraf, Leiden University

**LOCALLY-BASED INTERMEDIARIES AND FOREIGN AGENTS
DURING THE VOC'S SLAVE TRADING COMMISSIONS IN THE
EIGHTEENTH-CENTURY INDIAN OCEAN**

This paper discusses the agency, activities and achievements of Malagasy intermediaries (interpreters, brokers and officials) during the VOC's slave trading voyages on the North-Western coast of Madagascar during the seventeenth- and eighteenth-centuries. It attempts to reconceptualise the role of Indigenous intermediaries in the history of the Company's slave trading voyages in the western Indian Ocean. It brings the activities and agency of intermediaries, often invisible in the mediated accounts of VOC commissioners – the ships' journals or *skeepsjoernalen* – to the foreground of the intermediated encounters between the Company's slave trading parties and Malagasy intermediaries and elites. Michael Reidy's analysis of the role of intermediaries in the contestation of VOC power – the overarching research question – is supported by visible case studies which examine the power relations between VOC intermediaries, Malagasy intermediaries and elites and also enslaved people on the fringes of the Company's trading empire.

MICHAEL C. REIDY

Australian Catholic University, Melbourne

Michael C. Reidy is a South African PhD candidate at Australian Catholic University in Melbourne. He is busy writing his chapters on the role of intermediaries during VOC slave trading voyages in the western Indian Ocean during the seventeenth and eighteenth centuries. He has published papers and chapters on VOC slave trading at Madagascar, illicit slave trading during the first British occupation of the Cape in 1800 and made pioneering contributions of data to the Transatlantic Slave Trade Database and slavevoyages.org website.

CIRCULATION OF CAMPHOR IN THE VOC WORLD: TRADE, KNOWLEDGE AND REPRESENTATION IN NETWORKS

This article explores the ambiguity and circulation of “camphor,” a term conflating camphor and borneol in premodern Eurasia, as a lens for cross-cultural knowledge exchange between the 17th and 19th centuries. Drawing on Dutch East India Company records, Jesuit correspondence, and travel writings, it traces how camphor moved from China to Korea, Japan, and Europe, mediated by war, trade, and missionary networks. The study highlights diverse “images” of camphor, textual depictions in Chinese pharmacopeias and Japanese natural histories, botanical specimens shared among VOC physicians and Jesuit missionaries, and transplanted trees in Dutch gardens, revealing how commerce and competition shaped its identification. The research endeavors to reframe camphor as a case study of early modern global exchange, emphasizing the interplay of commerce, culture, and knowledge production beyond linear narratives of scientific classification. This appendix presents the experimental procedures for tracing camphor as a commodity in Inventory 1.04.21 (items 829–974), integrating digital-humanities methods to demonstrate reproducible approaches to archival data analysis.

HUANG XIANTING

University of Macau

Huang Xianting is a first-year PhD student in the Department of History at the University of Macau, with research interests in maritime history and the history of medicine. Huang’s primary concern is how materia medica catalogued, transmitted, and transformed by Jesuit missionaries and the Dutch East India Company (VOC) during the seventeenth and eighteenth centuries, situating the Indian Ocean as a central framework for exchanges of materials and knowledge. Huang is currently developing a project and article on the transfer of mineral remedies, medical catalogues, and transplantation within early modern network between the Netherlands, the Cape of Good Hope, and Batavia.

AT THE MARGINS OF EUROPEAN KNOWLEDGE: LOCAL GUIDES’ CONTRIBUTIONS TO VOC NAVIGATION DURING THE EIGHTEENTH CENTURY

Previously remaining at the edges of academic discourse, this article aims to bring local guides to the centre of analysis. Previous research acknowledged their presence but rarely examined their identities, areas of operation, treatment, or compensation. This neglect is striking, considering the VOC’s reliance on safe navigation as a cornerstone of its commercial success and its dependence on local guides to navigate unfamiliar waters. Using a corpus of previously overlooked archival material from the GLOBALISE Archives, this article demonstrates how local guides occupied a unique position along multiple boundaries. They operated between land and sea, providing coastal guidance whenever European cartographic

knowledge and navigational experience proved unreliable or insufficient. At the same time, they remained on the periphery of the VOC's labour system as temporary participants. Despite their liminal social, spatial, and contractual positions, local guides were highly valued and well compensated, often earning more than VOC sailors. They facilitated the movement of vessels, personnel, and cargo across the Company's global network. Consequently, the VOC's commercial success and the development of navigational science depended not only on European Company servants, but also crucially on the knowledge, expertise, and labour of local guides providing ad hoc navigational assistance.

ROMÉE VAN OOSTENBRUGGE

Utrecht University

Romée van Oostenbrugge graduated cum laude with a Research Master's in Art History from Utrecht University in September 2025. Following graduation, Romée conducted research on local guides employed by the VOC, focusing on their work and labour conditions as part of her interest in maritime and colonial history. She also contributed as a research assistant to the NWO-XS project Innovation in Ship Design in the Age of Sail and gave a lecture on an eighteenth-century globe at Centraal Museum Utrecht in 2024. An article based on her research on local guides is forthcoming in the *Tijdschrift voor Zeegeschiedenis*.

RECASTING THE TERMS OF EMPIRE: INDIGENOUS TRANSLATORS AND SCRIBES IN THE VOC ARCHIVES, AND HOW THEY MEDIATED THE LEGAL VOCABULARY THROUGH TREATY MAKING IN SOUTHEAST ASIA

This paper foregrounds the pivotal yet overlooked role of indigenous translators in treaty-making practices between the VOC and Southeast Asian rulers. It focuses on the translation of mid-eighteenth-century treaties between the Company and the Javanese empire of Mataram, and shows how a Javanese ulama, working as a VOC-clerk and interpreter, actively mediated and reshaped the treaties' vocabulary, syntax and meaning. Examining the bilingual Dutch-Javanese treaty texts alongside contemporary Javanese court chronicles, the paper elucidates translation as a highly politicised act of reinterpretation to accommodate divergent readings of the agreements within both Dutch and Javanese legal-political frameworks.

Rather than directly attempting to translate the VOC's juridical assertions, the translator systematically rendered them into Javanese idioms of reconciliation, guardianship, and voluntary entrustment, thereby domesticating the treaty texts and making them compatible within cyclical Javanese understandings of political decline, restoration, and renewal and palatable to Javanese elites. This allowed the latter to preserve the continuity and legitimacy of Javanese kingship, while the VOC derived its sovereignty claims from the very same texts.

Centring translators as historical actors, the paper argues that empire was not imposed solely through military force or European legal doctrine, but diplomatically negotiated and embedded in local politics and linguistically co-produced by translators and clerks at the moment of its making.

MAARTEN MANSE

Linnaeus University

Maarten Manse (PhD 2021, Leiden University) is a historian specialised in colonialism in Southeast Asia. He is currently a researcher at Linnaeus University in Sweden, working on treaty-making, intercultural diplomacy and legal interaction in Southeast Asia.

SESSION 3B

GLOBAL-MICRO HISTORIES
AND COLONIAL STRUCTUREThu 5 March 09.00 - 10.40
Max Nettleau room

Chair: Nira Wickramasinghe, Leiden University
Session coordinator: Britt van Duijvenvoorde, International Institute of Social History

LOCAL LIVES, GLOBAL STORIES: STUDYING THE VOC FACTORIES IN BENGAL, 1600-1800

The Dutch East India Company (VOC) settled in different parts of the Indian Ocean world and left scars of battles, violence, servitude and slavery. But they also traded simultaneously in different commodities, sailed to and from different port cities, administered villages, built gardens, factories and cemeteries with the help of those very people over whom they exercised power. These local actors were a crucial part of the banal stories of early-modern Dutch settlements. Yet very little is known about them today. Is there a way to know more about the ordinary people who lived in and around these settlements and interacted daily with the VOC? It is in quest of narrating the tales of these people that I explore the VOC archives through moments of conflict and tension. Through cases of villagers and their disputes over landed property using pattas under the Company's zamindari as well as petitions presented by weavers and other intermediaries involved in the Company's textile trade, I show how these people interacted with the VOC. By collecting fragments of their lives from legal cases and petitions, I argue that their local lives were affected significantly by the global changes in history.

BYAPTI SUR

Thapar Institute of Engineering and Technology, India

Byapti Sur is an Assistant Professor of History at Thapar University in Patiala, Punjab in India. She received her Ph.D. from Leiden University in 2019. Her doctoral thesis focussed on the encounter of the VOC with the local people of Mughal Bengal in the seventeenth century. She has also worked for the National Archives in the Hague, the IISG in Amsterdam and recently completed a visiting fellowship with the CAPASIA project in EUI, Italy in 2025. She has completed her M.A. in History from Jawaharlal Nehru University in New Delhi and her B.A. from Jadavpur University in Kolkata in India.

CAREL DE MIRANDO: A MICROHISTORY OF THE SERVICE OF AN ADMINISTRATIVE OFFICIAL IN DUTCH CEYLON

This study explores the story of an administrative official in Dutch Ceylon, Carel de Mirande. He was an Interpreter working for the Dutch East India Company in Dutch Ceylon. This study uses the Dutch East India Company (VOC) archives, more specifically the collection titled *Overgekomen Brieven en Papieron*, to reconstruct the work life of Carel de Mirande. The VOC archive presents a multi-faceted account of the service of de Mirande. On the one hand, he was one of the most efficient officers in Mahabadde, the Department related to Cinnamon, that successfully achieved the cinnamon targets expected in the period. He was considered as an efficient officer and the natives have requested the reinstatement of him in his office and to adopt the systems that he employed. On the other hand, he was one of the most corrupted colonial servants of the time. He was accused of taking bribes; of favouritism and discrimination; of extortion and of intimidation of the native cinnamon peelers. The story of de Mirande and the petitions against him reflect the social life of the cinnamon peelers, and the nature of Dutch colonial administration and the injustices natives had to face during this period. This story sheds light to the everyday social life under the Dutch administration, where a group of natives adopted to the system of bribing to the officials to exempt from work. It also shows the way in which the natives had to face injustices in the hands of lascarins, (indigenous soldiers) and Dutch officials. However, a critical reading of the archives would suggest that the natives were not passive receptors for these injustices. In fact, they were politically active against these injustices. They engaged in petition writing and sought relief from the Dutch administration. The natives were active agents of change rather than passive receptors of these injustices. In conclusion, this study although focuses on the story of Carel de Mirande, uncovers the corruption, injustices faced by the natives in everyday life and the political practices of the natives against these injustices during Dutch colonial administration in Ceylon.

RIVINDU DE ZOYSA

University of Colombo, Sri Lanka

Rivindu de Zoysa is a Lecturer (Probationary) of Department of History, University of Colombo. He obtained his Bachelors' and Master's degrees from the University of Colombo. He is an Attorney-at-Law of the Supreme Court of Democratic Socialist Republic of Sri Lanka. He is a researcher in the project, "Whose Law? Addressing injustice in the entangled histories of Sri Lanka- the Netherlands and advancing the practices of provenance research" and research assistant in the project "COLOMBO: Layered Histories in a Global South City."

WOMEN IN THE VOC ARCHIVE: PATRIARCHY AND PRESENCE IN DUTCH FORMOSA

In the 17th-century VOC world, patriarchal norms governed law, family, economy, and colonial administration. The archive reflects this reality, often presenting women only in relation to men—as wives, widows, mothers, or dependents. Current research challenges how later historians might have reinforced these patriarchal perspectives by taking the archive at face value, producing the impression that women had little or no role in colonial society. Yet, when read differently, the archive reveals traces of women’s presence, roles, and agency. In this sense, “patriarchy” is not only a social structure but also a historiographical lens imposed by both archival authors and subsequent scholarship. This presentation examines how women are represented in the VOC archive, with particular attention to a 17th-century narrative from Dutch Formosa (Tayouan factory), and enlarges the scope of field how widows have been presented in the archive. Methodologically, it combines close textual analysis with contextual inquiry. The presentation highlights how women’s presence—often marginalized or erased in later historiography—can be recovered through their relational appearances in the archive. The aim is not simply to rethink patriarchy as a historiographical construct, but to develop strategies for re-reading archives that allow women’s voices, agency, and positions to re-emerge, even within male-centered records. In the current climate this study speaks to wider debates in colonial history, archival studies, or gender historiography, demonstrating how critical reading practices can unsettle patriarchal frameworks and recover alternative perspectives from the margins of the historical record.

ANN HEYLEN

National Taiwan Normal University

Ann Heylen is a professor in the Department of Taiwan Culture, Languages and Literature, National Taiwan Normal University (NTNU), and executive director of the International Taiwan Studies Center (ITSC) at the College of Liberal Arts, NTNU. She is a founding member of the European Association of Taiwan Studies (EATS) (2004–present), editor-in-chief of *East Asian Journal of Popular Culture* (EAJPC) and associate editor of the *International Journal of Asia-Pacific Studies* (IJAPS, Malaysia). She publishes on topics covering the history and historiography of Taiwan with special attention to Dutch Formosa, the Japanese colonial period (1895–1945). She is currently working on projects exploring Formosa media narratives through digital newspaper corpora, and revisiting 17th century VOC source material in the China Seas (GLOBALISE project, Huygens Institute, Amsterdam).

SUCCESSION, ADOPTION, AND POWER: RANIS IN MALABAR DURING THE DUTCH PERIOD

This paper examines the power and role of royal women, or ranis, in succession during the period of Dutch presence in Malabar. Through three case studies, the paper examines if and how ranis could increase their power in the late seventeenth and early eighteenth-century Malabar. Asvati Tirunal, Rani of Attingal and regent of Travancore, a Rani of Cochin and a Rani of Alangadu are examined. Based on these three women, the paper argues that ranis derived significant economic and military resources and power from the possession of their cherikkallu. They could increase this power by carrying out strategic adoptions and forming alliances. This allowed ranis to have considerable autonomous power, separate from the raja.

ROSALIE OUDSHOORN

Leiden University

Rosalie Oudshoorn is an MA student in Colonial and Global History at Leiden University's Institute for History in the Netherlands. She conducts research on ranis and the workings of the matrilineal system of inheritance in Malabar. She is currently writing her MA thesis on the position of ranis in Malabar using the VOC archives.

SESSION 3C

**(RE)CONNECTING HISTORIES – VOC,
ATLANTIC AND IBERIAN EMPIRES**Thu 5 March 09.00 - 10.40
Posthumus room

Chair: Pepijn Brandon, International Institute of Social History
Session coordinator: Bethany Warner, International Institute of Social History

TRACING DIPLOMATIC INTERMEDIARIES IN THE VOC ARCHIVES

The figure of the “go-between” or local intermediary has become firmly established as a staple of global history research since the turn of the twenty-first century. Whether as knowledge brokers, translators, informants, or political liaisons, go-betweens are customarily described as both ubiquitous and liminal, their presence all-pervasive yet slippery both in an archival sense and – perhaps therefore – in our historical narratives. Drawing on recent developments in diplomatic history, including efforts to globalise our understandings of early modern diplomatic structures and practices, this paper will revisit the roles of Asian and European intermediaries in the diplomatic activities of the Dutch East India Company in Mughal India. Combining previous research on VOC diplomacy, conducted using traditional methods, with new explorations using the GLOBALISE research portal, it will explore the possibilities digitisation offers for gaining a fuller understanding of the roles and agency of actors with a marginal presence in the archive. The paper will reflect on aspects of process as well as on (provisional) research findings, seeking to flesh out the existing picture of the VOC’s integration into Mughal social and political structures.

GUIDO VAN MEERSBERGEN

University of Warwick

Guido van Meersbergen is an Associate Professor in Early Modern Global History at the University of Warwick, where he served as the director of the Global History and Culture Centre (2021-2025). He is a co-editor of the *Journal of Global History* and a coordinator of the Global Diplomacy Network. His research focuses on the presence of the Dutch and English East India Companies in South Asia, early modern diplomacy, and global travel. He is the author of *Ethnography and Encounter: The Dutch and English East India Companies in Seventeenth-Century South Asia* (Brill: 2022) and co-editor of *Trading Companies and Travel Knowledge in the Early Modern World* (Routledge: 2022). He recently co-edited a special issue of *Studies in Travel Writing* on “Travel Studies and the Decolonial Turn” (2024).

PLANTING ADDICTIONS: OPIUM TRADE AND THE COLONIAL EXPANSION OF THE VOC IN ASIA

This paper draws on archival sources located in the Netherlands, Indonesia, and China to examine the Dutch East India Company's (VOC) opium trade in Asia and its role in the consolidation of colonial hegemony. Departing from prevailing narratives that emphasise the British East India Company's opium smuggling and portray China as a passive participant drawn into global trade—often framing the two Opium Wars as the watershed of China's semi-colonial era—this paper argues that opium occupied a central position in Dutch and British imperial expansion. The circulation of opium in Asia was neither incidental nor a contingent historical event, but part of an intentional commercial and legal strategy shaped by VOC corporate governance and Dutch imperial policy. Positioning opium as the material basis for corporate colonialism, this paper interrogates how opium cultivation, trade, and wars articulated a triangular trade structure between East Asia, the Indian subcontinent, and Europe. It also analyses how contestations over opium trade rights shaped the transfer of colonial hegemony from the Netherlands to Britain, while entrenching a social and economic order rooted in colonial extraction across Asia.

ZHONGHUA DU

University of Amsterdam

Zhonghua Du is a PhD candidate at the Amsterdam Center for International Law. In 2024, she was a Kathleen Fitzpatrick Visiting Fellow at the Laureate Programme on Global Corporations and International Law in University of Melbourne. She obtained her bachelor's degree from Peking University and her master's degree from the University of Oxford.

THE ASIAN ENSLAVED AT THE INTERSECTIONS BETWEEN EUROPEAN ARCHIVES, CA. 1663

The latest literature on the Spanish Empire's Asian slaves has made limited or no use of the VOC archives. Instead, this literature emphasizes colonial Manila's Iberian connections with Goa, Malacca, and Macau. In contrast, this paper breaks new ground by utilizing the Globalise project's investment in HTR and digital access alongside the author's own R-based construction of digital databases of the tens of thousands of seventeenth-century government grants registered in colonial Manila. By June of 1663, Spain's empire in Asia had contracted around its colonial capital in fear of a Chinese invasion from a newly minted ruler of Taiwan. In its rush to Manila's defense, it conceded Ternate to the VOC, ending over half a century's struggle over the Moluccan spice islands. Despite the Spanish governor general's top-down intentions however, his subordinates still in Ternate continued to skirmish against the VOC leading one observer to complain about "Jezuitse pater, sergeant-majoor en andere kale schrobbers (Jesuit father, sargento mayor, and other bald miscreants)" who were tricking

slaves on the run from the Dutch by promising them freedom, only to later sell them in Manila. In early modern southeast Asia, both conflict and commerce created the conditions that propelled people into enslavement. This paper collects the VOC's observations (passing as well as predatory) about individuals enslaved by the Spanish empire. It then zeroes in on three cases, fully contextualizing them within both Dutch and Spanish contexts in Asia. These cases include: (1) the above Jesuit trading in slaves; (2) a militia company of freed South Asians guarding Manila's walls; and (3) the VOC enslavement / re-enslavement of captured indigenous Filipinos. Chasms, logistical and linguistic, impede the wholistic study of early modern enslavement in Asia. They interrupt the data-linkages necessary to study historical flows of forced labor, which were necessarily transimperial. This paper throws a rope across that divide, allowing the scholar to give direct attention not only to the exposed cliff faces of each collection, but also to the negative-space---often an indigenous Asian space---at which both sides hint. What did it mean to be enslaved at the tail end of Spain's guerra viva (live war) with the VOC? When war unmasks power, how do the enslaved negotiate their condition?

NICHOLAS C. SY

University of Philippines Diliman and Radboud University Nijmegen

Nicholas Sy is assistant professor at the Department of History, University of the Philippines Diliman. On leave, Nicholas is pursuing his doctorate at Radboud University Nijmegen under Prof. dr. Jan Kok and dr. Dries Lyna. His project looks statistically and culturally at slave experiences in the seventeenth century and problematizes the reductive views with which scholars have conceptualized slavery in the Philippines and the global Spanish Empire. In the fall of 2023, he went to Princeton University as a VSRC under Dr. Christina Lee of the Department of Spanish and Portuguese. In 2025, he was a doctoral fellow at the University of Bonn's Center for Dependency & Slavery Studies.

SESSION 4A

MEMORY, CULTURE
AND THE ARCHIVEThu 5 March 13.00 - 14.30
Nikolaevsky room*Chair: Lotte Baltussen, Huygens Institute**Session coordinator: Bethany Warner, International Institute of Social History***FROM ARCHIVES TO ARTEFACTS: NEGOTIATING VOC CULTURAL MEMORIES IN AUSTRALIA THROUGH THE DUTCH SHIPWRECK ARTEFACTS**

The Dutch East India Company (VOC) played a crucial role in mapping parts of Australia prior to Captain Cook's arrival on the continent. The part borne by the Dutch in Australia's history is etched in the continent's cultural memory through memorials, commemorative rituals, and museum exhibitions. This paper focuses on the VOC's shipwrecks and its artefacts off the coast of Western Australia and the salvaged objects from the wreck sites. It asks how and in what ways did these wrecks and artefacts influenced the cultural memory and historical understanding of the early modern Indian Ocean world and the Dutch's role in the history of Australia.

Drawing on a several array of primary sources, the paper explores how these wrecks are narrated, curated, and memorialised as part of an effort to situate Australia's place within global maritime history. Furthermore, Dondy analyses the formation of these VOC cultural memories as part of a complex, layered, and oft contradictory attempts to challenge the Anglo-centric cultural memories of Australia and to frame an inclusive, pre-British history of Australia. However, these attempts often remain embedded within the settler-colonial ethos of the continent. This research paper contributes to the growing literature on the colonial legacies of VOC as reproduced through institutionalised memories such as salvaged wrecks and curated artefacts.

DONDY PEPITO RAMOS*Australian Catholic University and University of the Philippines Diliman*

Dondy Pepito G. Ramos II is an instructor from the University of the Philippines Diliman, working on a PhD at the Australian Catholic University (ACU) under the Australian Research Council (ARC) Linkage Project called 'Mobilising Dutch East India Company Collections for New Global Stories.' This PhD project is a comparative analysis on the commemoration of the Spanish Empire in the Philippines and the Dutch East India Company in Australia.

DECENTRING COLONIAL HISTORIES: GEOVISUALISING OOSTENBURG'S ENTANGLEMENTS WITH COLONIAL EXPLOITATION

Geovisualisation of colonial interconnections can be a valuable means of counteracting the dominant memory of colonialism. However, using colonial archive data in the form of 'archival encounters' (Agostinho, 2019) can cause discomfort as there is a risk of reproducing coloniality (Quijano, 2000). Nelo Schmalen proposes a theoretical framework that connects postcolonial geographical perspectives on European cities and colonial archives with critical geo-visualisation and cartography methods. Nelo asks: what were Oostenburg's entanglements with colonial exploitation, and how can geovisualisation serve as a critical method in this context?

This empirical study uses GLOBALISE data sets to produce a geovisualisation of the interconnections resulting from the ships built at Oostenburg's former VOC shipyard (1660–1795). Nelo interprets these ships as infrastructure for colonial exploitation that connected Amsterdam with places where people were forcibly displaced to and/or exploited. The aim of this study is to highlight the colonial exploitation historically associated with the Oostenburg district of Amsterdam, which has been overlooked in the cityscape. This contributes to the rethinking of European urban spaces (Ha/Pickert, 2022) and the decentre of European harbour cities and archival work by providing an exemplary analysis of how Oostenburg was shaped and connected through colonial exploitation.

NELO A. SCHMALEN

European-University Flensburg, Germany

Nelo Schmalen is currently a Rosa-Luxemburg-Stiftung scholarship holder in the research group "Crisis and Social-Ecological Transformation" and has completed an interdisciplinary Master's degree in Transformation Studies at the Europa Universität Flensburg (M.A.). Prior to this, Nelo worked as an architect and studied architecture. This paper contribution at the GLOBALISE conference forms part of the second article of a cumulative dissertation in Integrative Geography. In it, Nelo combines critical perspectives on postcolonial European port cities with the visualisation and analysis of the coloniality of urban structures and geographical memory research focusing on colonial exploitation.

UNRAVELLING LIFEWORLDS: FARMERS AND CONSUMERS OF BLACK PEPPER

This paper explores the intersection of ethnographic design research and critical fabulation as a means of creatively engaging with the postcolonial complexities of international trade of black pepper between India and the Netherlands. Drawing on multi-sited ethnography, fieldwork with pepper farmers, labourers, and stakeholders in Shimoga, alongside consumer

research in Dutch supermarkets and surveys in Eindhoven was conducted. The research foregrounds personal narratives, lived experiences, and oral histories that reveal falling pepper prices, exploitative labour dynamics, consumer detachment from production processes, investigate alienation and the erasure of historical context in everyday commodities. Methodologically, the project applies Saidiya Hartman's concept of critical fabulation, blending historical fact with imaginative speculation to construct alternative narratives that challenge dominant accounts. The speculative proposition : "What if black pepper had remained a global currency?" offers an imaginative re-framing of colonial trade, exposing how historical erasures continue to shape contemporary realities of labour and consumption. The project culminated in a design installation that included a speculative artefact that is a "black pepper wallet", and a historical timeline of spice trade. Ultimately, the project argues that design can meaningfully contribute to postcolonial discourse by situating subjectivity, ethnographic engagement, and speculative methods at the centre of inquiry.

POORVI PRABHAKAR GARAG

Independent scholar

Poorvi Prabhakar Garag is a strategic social designer, researcher and educator. Poorvi crafts tools, frameworks, objects of art and design to generate positive impact on multi-stakeholder ecosystems; across eco-socio-political complexities. With a deep commitment to creating social impact and change, Poorvi works with industrial design, critical design thinking and design research skills informed by the fields of anthropology, sociology, futurology, and decolonial studies. As an artist and designer, Poorvi's work manifests as workshops or designed objects, text and images, exhibitions and, as a researcher, Poorvi's work is found as workshops, academic papers, conference presentations and books.

SESSION 4B

LOCAL DIVERSITIES AND
COLONIAL TENSIONSThu 5 March 13.00 - 14.30
Max Nettleau room*Chair: Kathryn Wellen, KITLV**Session coordinator: Louie Buana, Leiden University/KITLV***THE TWO FATES OF PLURAL SOCIETIES RECONSIDERED: ACTOR-CENTERED PERFORMATIVE REPRODUCTION OF VOC PLAKKAATEN IN SEVENTEENTH-CENTURY CAPE AND FORMOSA.**

This paper examines the performative nature and processes of reproduction of seventeenth-century plakkaaten (ordinances) issued by the Dutch East India Company (VOC) within colonial settlements. The original research design aimed to trace how historical events in Formosa influenced company policy implementation at the Cape of Good Hope, but methodological adjustments became necessary due to limitations in the Batavia-centered archival record.

Rather than relying on a linear tracing of archival documents, the study emphasises the roles of multiple actors, ranging from employees at the Cape to Han Chinese merchants in Formosa, in interpreting, implementing, and especially violating Company ordinances. Such practices not only reveal the capacities and limits of local authority in different settlements, but also actively shaped the continued circulation and iterative reproduction of plakkaaten across the VOC network. By “decentering” Batavia as the sole information hub and foregrounding the performative and iterative dimensions of ordinance enforcement, this study proposes a novel actor-centered approach that connects company history, global history, and studies of governance practices.

LAP KAN AU*National Taiwan Normal University*

Lap Kan Au is a PhD student at National Taiwan Normal University and an incoming visiting scholar at Radboud University. Lap Kan Au’s research focuses on the seventeenth-century Dutch East India Company. Lap Kan Au has published a journal article titled “The Clash of Trade Ideologies: Revisiting the Battle of Liaoluo Bay through the Lens of Hans Putmans’ Interpretation of Vrijen Handel and the Ming Tributary System” and has participated in the project “From Formosa to the Cape: Seventeenth-Century Dutch-Language Historical Materials and Digitalisation.” Lap Kan Au also have experience assisting in the organisation of a conference and contributing as a translator to a scholarly volume.

MURDER IN THE PLANTATIONS: THE CHINESE CIVIL WAR ON RIAU (1786-92)

When Riau was reconquered by the Dutch East India Company (VOC) in 1787, most of the Malays and Bugis had long decamped, leaving behind a large but rowdy population of Chinese divided along ethnic lines. While outwardly submitting to the new authority, the souring of relations between the Hokkiens and the Teochews, and a brewing squabble over the leadership of the growing Chinese community, soon led to the trading of insults, a series of murders, and the outbreak of conflict. Based on a series of missives between Melaka and the Dutch residents on Riau, Chinese letters written by the warring parties seeking intervention from the Company (公班衙), and other reports collected in the archives of Jakob van Kal, this article sheds light on Dutch struggles in managing a unique frontier society, and highlights how ethnic rivalry, local dissensions, and trade disputes among the overseas Chinese came to the fore in late-eighteenth century Riau (廖內).

BENJAMIN J.Q. KHOO

Independent scholar

Benjamin J.Q. Khoo, M.A. is currently an independent scholar based in Singapore. He has published several articles on the history of Singapore and the Malay world before 1800. His research interests include the circulation of knowledge and cross-cultural and diplomatic encounters in early modern Asia.

MAPPING THE EVERYDAY LIVES OF A SUBALTERN COMMUNITY: THE MUKKUVAS OF MALABAR IN THE VOC ARCHIVES

This study reconstructs the social history of the Mukkuvas, a marginalized coastal fishing community of Malabar, through the largely unexplored archives of the Verenigde OostIndische Compagnie (VOC) in the eighteenth century. Although the Mukkuvas have remained largely invisible in colonial historiography, the meticulous administrative records of the VOC offer rare insights into their everyday lives, internal organization, and shifting social positions. By reading these sources critically and “beyond the grain,” this research examines how caste, religion, and colonial governance intersected to shape Mukkuva lives. This study treats Christianity as a central theme, which created a dual juridical system wherein Christian Mukkuvas became VOC subjects, while non-Christian Mukkuvas remained under customary law. The study analyzes the involvement of Mukkuvas in slave networks, their occupational diversification beyond fishing into shipbuilding, maritime labor, and agriculture, and the functioning of community institutions such as councils of elders and caste leaders. The findings challenge the notion of the Mukkuvas as uniformly “fringe-dwellers,” revealing instead a stratified community in which a small Christian elite leveraged colonial structures for social mobility, while the majority continued to experience exploitation and precarity. The paper highlights both continuity and change in caste hierarchies under colonial rule and demonstrates the value of VOC archives for

writing social histories of marginalized communities.

LIJA MARY KAMBAKKARAN JOSEPH

Leiden University

Lija Mary Kambakkaran Joseph is a Cosmos Malabaricus Fellow of Colonial and Global History at the University of Leiden, where she is part of the broader project of decolonization of Dutch Archives. Holding also an MA from the Centre For Historical Studies, Jawaharlal Nehru University (JNU), her primary research area is maritime social and cultural history, with a focus of historicizing transnational cultural exchanges and negotiations of Christianity in the Indian Ocean and beyond. Currently, in Leiden, her work examines the Malabar society during the transition from the Portuguese to the Dutch period, with a focus on questions of intra-religious power dynamics, influence of caste and cultural expressions.

SESSION 4C

**COMMODITY FRONTIERS,
ENVIRONMENT AND RESISTANCE**Thu 5 March 13.00 - 14.30
Posthumus room*Chair: Catia Antunes, Leiden University**Session coordinator: Pichayapat Naisupap, Leiden University***BY ALL MEANS NECESSARY: THE ORGANIZATION OF INDIGO
PRODUCTION AND RESISTANCE UNDER THE VOC**

This paper examines the role of indigo in the emergence of the European calico printing industry and analyzes the Dutch East India Company's efforts to control its production and trade during the seventeenth and eighteenth centuries. Initially imported from India, printed cotton textiles stimulated a process of import substitution in Europe and became central to the rise of industrial capitalism. Indigo, an essential high-value dye for cotton printing, was a critical link in this global production chain as a colonial staple. As European demand increased, merchant companies sought to secure reliable supplies under their own colonial control, thereby reshaping production sites across Asia and the Atlantic world.

While existing scholarship has largely focused on nineteenth-century indigo economies, especially in Bengal, the earlier VOC engagement with indigo has received limited attention. This paper addresses this gap, arguing that the VOC proactively intervened in indigo production in response to resistance by producers or traders. The company gathered and formalized indigo production knowledge, which they then implemented by directly controlling its production under a system of *corvée* capitalism on Java.

JENS AURICH*International Institute of Social History and University of Amsterdam*

Jens Aurich is a PhD researcher at the International Institute of Social History (IISH) and the University of Amsterdam. His doctoral project investigates how workers' resistance to exploitation shaped the first capitalist global production chain of printed cotton textiles. He analyzes the role of collective labor action in driving institutional, organizational, and technological innovation, as well as in processes of knowledge appropriation within European calico printing and colonial dyestuff production. In addition to his dissertation research, he contributes to the IISH Global Hub Labor Conflicts project, where he develops digital workflows to extract and structure data on collective action from digitized historical sources.

SPICE ROUTES TO SCARRED LANDSCAPES: HOW DUTCH COLONIAL CORPORATION RESHAPED WORLD LANDSCAPES.

This presentation examines how Dutch colonial corporate expansion in the Indian Ocean and Atlantic worlds transformed environments and societies into commodity frontiers. Using an ArcGIS StoryMap as both a method and narrative device, it traces how the Dutch East India Company (VOC) and the West India Company (WIC) engineered extractive landscapes through land appropriation, labour control, and ecological reorganisation. Rather than approaching colonialism solely as a political or economic project, this presentation conceptualises it as an ecological and spatial system. Dutch chartered companies constructed commodity frontiers through mapping, fortification and legislation. These processes produced what is described as a colonial environmental footprint—the long-term environmental transformations generated by colonial systems of extraction. By tracing these “scarred landscapes” from plantation monocultures to contemporary biodiversity loss, this presentation argues that a decolonial environmental history must grapple with how colonial capitalism fundamentally rewired human–environment relationships, leaving a spatial legacy that continues to structure environmental injustice today.

LINU DANIELKUTTY

Utrecht University

Linu Danielkuty is a PhD candidate at the Copernicus Institute of Sustainable Development (Utrecht University) with a background in environmental sciences. The research project, *Footprints of Colonialism*, explores the environmental consequences of colonial land-use systems. This StoryMap emerged during the development of my research proposal: the absence of colonial histories in traditional environmental science frameworks. By weaving archival sources together with spatial analysis, Linu Danielkuty aims to resituate environmental change within its historical context.

TRANS-IMPERIAL TRAVELS: THE QUEST TO COMMODIFY CACAO IN ISLAND SOUTHEAST ASIA

This paper argues that Mesoamerican cacao reveals the multi-faceted historical agencies of Southeast Asian growers that are often overlooked in histories of early modern knowledge production. Using recently digitised records from the Globalise project, the paper shows that Indonesian cultivators on Ambon and Ternate outmanoeuvred the VOC in the face of unsystematic Company policy. They deployed multiple strategies – at times commodifying cacao for their own profit, at other times continuing to practise subsistence cultures – that did not conform to Company interests or ambitions. Some cultivators, such as those in Ternate, produced cacao for the market, participating in their own forms of commodification that echo enduring trade networks world that predated European arrival. Others on Ambon continued to

grow cacao as a subsistence plant, evading Company attempts to commodify it for its own benefit. Finally, the paper argues that Indonesian cultivators developed knowledge about cacao's preferred ecologies and growing practices outside of the realm of Company surveillance, responding to transoceanic mobilities of cacao with creativity and adaptability. This positions Indonesian smallholders as knowledge producers in the early modern world, alongside European men who have been centre stage in historical narratives.

KATHLEEN BURKE

Instituto Ciências Sociais, Lisbon

Kathleen Burke is a historian of food, gender, and maritime empires in the Indian Ocean World. Her first book project, "Hearth of Empire: A History of Indian Ocean Cuisine", repositions colonial kitchens front and centre of global history, showing how they were spaces of power, knowledge production, and cultural exchange in the Dutch East India Company's empire in the Indian Ocean. Her current project, "Cultivating Connections" focuses on how Indigenous growers in the Indian Ocean were adapters and transformers of knowledge about American plants. Her latest publication is "Recultivating Connections in the Indian Ocean" in *Slavery and Abolition*.

SESSION 5A

MATERIAL CULTURE AND
DIPLOMACYThu 5 March 15.00 - 16.45
Nikolaevsky room*Chair: Alicia Schrikker, Leiden University**Session coordinator: Pepijn Trienekens, International Institute of Social History***SYMBOLIC ADOPTION OF DUTCH EAST INDIA COMPANY
MERCHANTS: TWO CASES FROM SEVENTEENTH-CENTURY VIETNAM**

In 1637, a Dutch East India Company ship led by Carel Hartsinck arrived in Tonkin (today's northern Vietnam), seeking to establish trade relations with the Trịnh rulers of the realm. There, following his audience with the court, Hartsinck was nominally adopted by Lord Trịnh Tráng as his son. Likewise, in 1651, following the visit of VOC official Willem Verstegen, Trịnh Tráng also sent his ambassadors to Batavia, indicating that he regarded the newly-appointed Governor-General Carel Reyniersz as his adopted son. Similar cases of such 'adoptions' can be found in neighbouring polities during that time as well.

This paper will present my findings regarding this practice, which, according to a Dutch author, was "a formality widespread in Southeast Asia, until recently [early twentieth century] in vogue" (Hendrik Pieter Nicolaas Muller 1917). The paper will look into two case studies in seventeenth-century Vietnam, examining the motives, historical contexts, and results of these symbolic 'adoptions'. What had prompted each side to form such a relation, and to what extent did it help them gain what they wanted? How was this practice linked to gift-giving, and how was it informed by the Vietnamese's Confucianist principles regarding familial duty?

PHAM THUY DUNG*Huygens Institute*

Pham Thuy Dung obtained an MA History degree from VU University Amsterdam, with a focus on Vietnamese and colonial histories. She currently works as a junior researcher for the GLOBALISE project, where she helps curate datasets on early modern places and ethno-religious groups featuring in the Dutch East India Company archives.

SAPPANWOOD FOR THE KING'S DEBT: MATERIAL AND THE STRUGGLING COOPERATION BETWEEN THE VOC AND THE SIAMESE COURT IN THE EARLY EIGHTEENTH CENTURY

According to VOC reports, by 1736 the debt of the Siamese king recorded in the Company's accounts had already accumulated to 379,159 guilders. This enormous sum naturally created unease regarding cooperation with the Siamese court. In fact, this massive debt was a financial "legacy" built up over several decades, and it became one of the most troublesome issues the VOC ever faced in Siam. Moreover, VOC employees also frequently complained about the Siamese court's inconsistency, unfair treatment of the Dutch, and capricious demands. Why, then, did the VOC still persist in diligently maintaining its relationship with Siam? This article seeks to answer this question from a material perspective and to situate VOC–Siam cooperation within a broader network of material exchange.

As early as 1709, the Siam–Dutch treaty stipulated that the Ayutthaya court was to repay its debts to the VOC in equal proportions of cash, tin, and sappanwood. Sappanwood, a red dye material, was reported by a VOC employee to be the most profitable commodity available to the Company in Siam at that time. Driven by the enormous demand for red colours in East Asian markets, it became a crucial element in the Company's entry into those markets. By tracing the history of sappanwood, this article examines English, Dutch, Thai, and Chinese sources to outline its formative role in the VOC's commercial enterprise, and to show how the market for sappanwood empowered its place of origin, Siam, in diplomacy. In doing so, it reconsiders the ways and motives through which the VOC engaged with Asian states.

ZIQUAN ZHOU

London School of Economics and Political Science

Ziquan Zhou is currently a PhD Candidate in the Department of International History at London School of Economics and Political Science, where her doctoral research is funded by the London Arts and Humanities Partnership. Her research interests span the history and literatures of East and Southeast Asia, global history, and material culture. Her current project uses the case of Siamese sappanwood to examine the interplay between natural landscapes, aesthetic trends, dyeing techniques, Asian commercial networks, and the modernization of Southeast Asia. It further explores how environmental history and material-culture studies may be brought together in global historical writing from a non-Eurocentric perspective.

ALL POLITICAL POWER COMES FROM THE BARREL OF A GUN: ARMS TRADING, GUN CONTROL, AND REVOLT IN AYUTTHAYA

This paper examines the VOC's role as a supplier of European firearms technology to the Kingdom of Ayutthaya. These transfers happened through diplomatic gift giving, which facilitated and mirrored regular trade between the king and the company. By tracing the significance of weapons as gifts across the reigns of three consecutive kings, this study illuminates both VOC and Siamese perspectives on the arms trade. The Siamese king's interest in weapons was situational, often tied to domestic crises. However, the VOC's uncertainty about the king's ability to repay debts incurred for these weapons complicated transactions. The pattern of weapons gifting suggests that firearms were primarily used to suppress domestic opponents rather than for foreign wars. Research on VOC arms trading has been hindered by fragmented archival sources, but new Handwritten Text Recognition (HTR) methods now enable the identification of scattered references. This advancement promises a deeper understanding of the VOC's approach to disseminating European weapons technology and its impact on non-European societies.

PHILIPP HUBER

International Institute of Social History and Radboud University Nijmegen

Philipp Huber is a PhD candidate at the International Institute of Social History and the Radboud University Nijmegen, as part of the NWO project The Global Business of Slave Trade: Patterns, Actors and Gains in the Early Modern Dutch and Iberian Slave Trade. He holds a MA in Colonial and Global History from Leiden University. He currently researches slavery and slave trading in eighteenth century Macau. Previously he researched Dutch weapons trading in Early Modern Atlantic Africa and Southeast Asia.

SESSION 5B

**COLONIAL EXPLOITATION:
 LAND AND PEOPLE**

*Thu 5 March 15.00 - 16.45
 Max Nettle room*

Chair: Joris van den Tol, Radboud University Nijmegen

Session coordinator: Ryhan M. Yazid, Kyoto University/KITLV

A FEMALE ALCHEMIST AND VOC'S MINING VENTURE IN SEVENTEENTH-CENTURY SUMATRA

This paper seeks to explore the intersection of mining, alchemical pursuit, and women's experience in the VOC, through the case study of the female alchemist Fronica Wijs's life and work. In the late 1660s, the VOC launched intensive mining operations for precious metals on the west coast of Sumatra. But the mining productivities had been consistently unsatisfactory since the beginning of the operation. Wijs came to the East Indies from Europe with her late husband in the late 1670s, who had been appointed to oversee the mining operation, but died en route. She successfully petitioned to go to the mining sites in Sumatra to produce gold for the Company alchemically. But her alchemical work at the Sumatran mines also caused controversies. I show that faced with uncertain economic and environmental conditions, alchemy emerged as productive knowledge for the VOC to interpret the natural world and explore resources. Yet, the processes through which alchemical knowledge and authority were constructed were frequently contested.

WENRUI ZHAO

University of Utah

Wenrui Zhao is a historian of science and medicine, with a focus on early modern northern Europe and its connections with the wider world, particularly Asia. She is an assistant professor at the University of Utah. Her current project studies the VOC's mining venture in Sumatra in the late seventeenth and early eighteenth centuries.

THE POLITICS OF HEALING: MEDICINE, BIOPOLITICS, AND THE DUTCH EAST INDIA COMPANY IN SRI LANKA

What role(s) did the medical establishment of the Dutch East India Company (VOC) played in its colonial encounters? What truth(s) does it reveal about the VOC's politics (or biopolitics), governance, profit and power? This study approaches these questions through postcolonial theoretical lenses, such as Michel Foucault's concept of power and biopolitics, and Edward Said's Orientalism. The analysis draws on the Dutch archives in Sri Lanka, such as the Dutch

Political Council Resolutions, records of Dutch (and foreign) physicians in Dutch Ceylon, and accounts of special envoys, sailors, and other visitors. Findings suggests that the Dutch exercised anatomo-politics by disciplining the body and practicing selective care: 'making live' some populations, particularly elite Dutch, employees of the company, and 'letting die' others for political, economic and strategic reasons. Indigenous knowledge and practices were sometimes appropriated and experimented with, but rarely recognized as authoritative, reflecting a clear epistemic hierarchy. Simultaneously, the Dutch medical practice was also a tool of diplomacy—by gifting medicine to the royal patients in Kandy. Medicine was also an economic tool, as the Dutch identified how their profit was affected by epidemics such as smallpox. This clearly demonstrate that colonial care was instrumental, conditional, and politically entangled, but not charity, public service or humanitarianism.

SANDUNIKA HASANGANI

Open University Sri Lanka

Sandunika Hasangani is a Senior Lecturer in the Department of Social Studies at the Open University of Sri Lanka. Her PhD research lies at the intersection of digital ethnography, political anthropology, and visual culture, with broader research interests in identity politics, colonial history, medical anthropology, and post-war Sri Lanka. As a recipient of the Silk Roads Youth Research Grant 2022-23, her recent research explores the history of medicine along the Silk Roads, with particular attention to Unani medical practices and their indigenisation across diverse cultural and religious contexts. She has published widely in leading academic journals and actively engages in interdisciplinary research and teaching.

SLAVERY AND DIS/ABILITY: CASE STUDIES FROM THE CAPE COLONY

Recent scholarship has foregrounded disability as a critical lens for understanding the embodied violence of slavery. Studies of the Caribbean and US South argue that slavery functioned as a system of enforced disablement: long-distance trafficking, harsh labour regimes, punishment, malnutrition, and disease systematically produced bodily and mental impairments. Disability was not incidental to slavery but integral to its mechanisms of discipline and extraction. At the same time, disability history has shifted from a medical to a social model, conceptualizing disability as produced through social structures and power relations. This perspective reframes slavery as a system that actively constructed categories such as able-bodied/disabled, productive/unproductive, and normal/abnormal — binaries deeply entangled with race and colonialism. In colonial contexts, dis/ability became synonymous with dependency, legitimating enslavement and racial hierarchies. These intersections have not yet been explored in the Cape Colony context. Through selected case studies from the Dutch and British periods (1652–1834), this paper examines punishment, im-

pairment, productivity, and self-invalidating to illuminate how disability was produced and managed within Cape slavery, contributing to the discussion on how to write new histories of colonial pasts.

KATE EKAMA

Stellenbosch University

Kate Ekama is a senior researcher at the Laboratory for the Economics of Africa's Past (LEAP), Stellenbosch University. Her work focuses on slavery at the Cape under the Dutch East India Company and in the British Empire. Kate's publications include articles in the *Journal of Southern African Studies*, *Slavery & Abolition* and *Enterprise & Society*. Her current work focusses on rebuilding enslaved people's lives through Slave Registers which is forthcoming in the *Journal of Interdisciplinary History*. This research is part of Project 1834 which combines credible historical research, public history and visual redress.

EVA MARIE LEHNER

Bonn Center for Dependency and Slavery Studies, Germany

Eva Marie Lehner is a postdoctoral researcher and lecturer at the Bonn Center for Dependency and Slavery Studies (BCDSS). Her work focuses on slavery studies, Dutch colonial history, early modern record-keeping, and gender history. Her PhD examined registration practices in early modern German parish registers, published in 2023. She currently researches slavery and resistance in the Dutch Cape Colony (1652–1795), emphasizing intersecting dependencies. Her publications include articles in *German History* (2026) and in *Slavery, Law and Religion in the Early Modern Period* (Brill, 2024), as well as forthcoming work on slavery, gender relations, and childhood at the Cape.

MOBILIZING AGAINST MOBILIZATION: RESISTANCE AGAINST COMMERCIAL ENSLAVEMENT IN ARAKAN, COROMANDEL, AND MALABAR.

Recent developments in global slavery studies have provided new conceptual bases to analytically compare different forms of enslavement across slavery regimes worldwide. Histories about resistance by enslaved and their allies, however, oftentimes lack a similar global scope. This paper explores resistance against enslavement from a global perspective in Arakan, Coromandel, and Malabar. The aim of this paper is twofold. Firstly, it follow recent trends in global slavery studies that have attempted to reconceptualize slavery, not as a (legal) institution, but as historically contextualized practices of "slaving" in distinct though globally comparable slavery regimes (Miller 2012; van Rossum 2021). The regions of choice — Arakan,

Coromandel, and Malabar — were sites in which local bondage systems intersected with slavery regimes oriented towards the exportation of enslaved individuals. A second intention of this paper, then, is to read resistance against enslavement in dialogue with these differently intersecting slavery regimes in the regions studied. Concretely, this paper attends to acts of resistance in which the immobilization of local bondage systems of import-oriented slave regimes clashed with mobilizing commercial slave trade regimes that aimed at the exportation of enslaved individuals.

BRITT VAN DUIJVENVOORDE

International Institute of Social History

Britt van Duijvenvoorde is a PhD researcher at the International Institute of Social History (IISH) and outreach manager of the Exploring Slave Trade in Asia (ESTA) project. She obtained a master's degree in Philosophy at Radboud University and in History at Leiden University. Her PhD is part of Matthias van Rossum's Vidi project *Resisting Enslavement: A Global Historical Approach to Slavery in the Dutch Atlantic and Asian Empire (1620-1815)*, in which she focuses on how enslaved individuals co-shaped and resisted against enslavability during the seventeenth and eighteenth centuries in the Indian Ocean context.

SESSION 5C

SCIENCE, ENVIRONMENT, AND
COLONIAL HISTORIESThu 5 March 15.00 - 16.45
Posthumus room

Chair: Jessie Wei-Hsuan Chen, Huygens Institute
Session coordinator: Nur'Ain Taha, Utrecht University

**UNSMOOTH SAILING IN SWALLEY: THE VOC'S HYDROGRAPHIES
OF LOCAL WATERSCAPES IN THE INDIAN OCEAN WORLD**

The roots of early modern geographic knowledge are deeply imbricated in extractive merchant capital. This paper deploys a combination of VOC archives, particularly shipping records and cartographies, in combination with the East India Company records, to locate early histories of docking points near the famed port of Surat on India's western coast. It deploys visual and navigational records of ships and their crew from the seventeenth century. This paper makes use of digitally available archives to present a case-study of representations of a docking point near Surat called the Swalley Hole. It argues that early modern oceanic trade, driven by an influx of colonial capital and commodities in the region, altered visions of the coast. In so doing, it rendering local geographies identifiable, pragmatic, and measurable, while making its lived stories and socio-religious landscape invisible. These are mostly keenly visible through hydrographic productions made in studios like the Vingboons of Amsterdam. When read against the immediacy of local shipping journals, the physical distance of such production houses from their geographical subjects becomes stark.

The long-winded mediation and circulation of the Dutch VOC's geographic knowledge also shows that such productions often wrote local actors out of their visions. But even in their reduced forms, these geographical representations allow us to think about how capital investments in trade and commodity circulation yielded. Both processes highlight the early modern hydrograph and geography in capital-driven and colonial sciences. In sum, they both devoured, reshaped, and also repopulated the coastal geography of the Indian Ocean. Tracing such time and capital-bound mobilities allows us to make geographic knowledge a historical problem, thus offering new frames for casting early modern encounters. In so doing, it contributes to the growing historiographies of early modern sciences and their deep ties with colonial and capitalist pasts.

APARAJITA DAS

University of California, Berkeley

Aparajita Das is a Ph.D. candidate at the Department of History who works on the environmental history of the Indian Ocean World, commodity trade and the intersection of agrarian frontiers of the Mughal Empire and Company states.

NO (HU)MAN IS AN ISLAND: THE CONSTRUCTION OF NATURE IN SOURCES FROM DUTCH MAURITIUS (1598-1710)

Bioprospecting, or the examination of the natural world for commercial purposes, was an essential instrument for the VOC in expanding its global power – a process leading to financial gain for some, loss of freedom for many, and far-reaching changes to the environments they inhabited. Taking Dutch Mauritius (1598-1710) as its starting point, this paper considers how early modern bioprospecting was shaped by the experience of colonial travel. How was Mauritian nature constructed in journals and reports? And what new insights can the case of Mauritius – a place of isolation, void of indigenous humans, in between two continents – bring us regarding the experience of travel in the VOC’s expansive network? It will be argued that closer attention for representations of nature in all its facets, but animal life in particular, can lead to new insights and – more importantly – new questions about colonial constructions of the non- and perhaps less-than-human. As such, this paper is an exercise in deconstructing the anthropocentric colonial knowledge system arising under the auspices of the VOC and encourages everyone to critically reformulate a new history of the VOC in which human actors are not apart from, but a part of nature.

ANNA BRUINS

University of Warwick

Anna Bruins is a historian of science, holding master’s degrees from Utrecht University and the University of Glasgow. She started her PhD at the University of Warwick in 2024. Her research project, provisionally titled *In Pursuit of Planting: Scientific Travel and the VOC's Bioprospective Quest in the Indian Ocean World*, focuses on the production of natural knowledge by VOC travellers, and their contributions to the rise of the Company’s plantation industries. Using a diverse range of travel writing, her research explores human-nonhuman relations. It pays particular attention to the colonial conceptualisation of nature in terms of ownership, value, and progress.

THROUGH THE LIFE OF CHILLIE, A FEMALE HUNTING ELEPHANT: UNCOVERING THE GLOCAL WORLD OF THE 'UNDERCLASS' ELEPHANTS IN DUTCH CEYLON

‘Chillie’ is the name of a female hunting elephant mentioned in a Dutch East India Company (VOC) document in 1733. This particular manuscript contains a witness statement from both European and local VOC employees, noting that the elephant Chillie had passed on from her old age not from any diseases. The name Chillie, with some variations, appears sporadically in VOC records as well as early modern Dutch prints. By tracing her life through these scattered references with the help of digital tools and also reading it alongside stories of other hunting

and working elephants, this paper seeks to uncover the world of 'underclass' elephants in Ceylon and to examine how such categorisation came into being. Drawing on approaches from 'global microhistory,' suggested by the historian Tonio Andrade, this paper argues that the world of 'underclass' elephants in Ceylon was shaped as much by the Sinhalese elephant tradition as by transregional entanglements of various elephant traditions across southern Asia. It further contends that the establishment of the Dutch power through the VOC in Ceylon effectively harnessed this world of 'underclass' elephants for its own benefit, which also involved lives of 'gentry' elephants.

PICHAYAPAT NAISUPAP

Leiden University

Pichayapat Naisupap, also known as Toh, is a PhD candidate at the Institute for History, Leiden University. Originally from Thailand, he obtained his bachelor's degree in Southeast Asian Studies from Thammasat University and master's degree in history from Chulalongkorn University in Bangkok. He further honed his professionalism as a historian with another master's degree in Colonial and Global History from the Institute for History at Leiden University. In 2021, he continued in this field by starting his PhD at the same institute. His PhD project explores the early modern Dutch Empire in global contexts of entanglements with different elephant traditions across Eurasia. He has published articles in different fields, ranging from social and cultural histories of Southeast Asia to global non-human, diplomatic, and intellectual histories of Eurasia.

SEVERE AND SCORCHING FEVERS: A STUDY OF EIGHTEENTH-CENTURY SHIP SURGEONS' JOURNALS

For this paper, fifteen eighteenth-century surgeon's journals were studied. The oldest dated from 1732, the newest from 1783. All journals except one were kept during the voyage from the Netherlands to Ceylon, via the Cape of Good Hope. The exception was a journal from 1778, that only covered the journey from the Cape to Ceylon. These journals contain a wealth of information not only about the diseases and conditions on board of the VOC ships, but also about the surgeons themselves and their patients. Surgeons were obliged to keep a journal by an instruction issued by the VOC in 1695 which formalized the surgeon's duties, and which was drawn up as a result of the high mortality rates on board the company vessels in the period 1690-1695. In this paper, a short explanation will be given about the medical care provided by the VOC and the state of medicine in the 18th century. Then some key findings from the journals will be presented and two particularly interesting journals will be discussed in more detail. Finally some areas of interest for further research will be pointed out.

LINDA ROBERTUS

Radboud University Nijmegen

Linda Robertus received her medical degree from the University of Groningen in 1996 and worked as a public health physician in tuberculosis control before moving to Australia in 2007, where she worked in research, medical education and as a medical writer. She completed a Bachelor of Arts at Griffith University, Brisbane, and started a Research Master Historical Studies at Radboud University in 2024. She has completed her International Research Internship at the GLOBALISE project at the Huygens Institute, and is currently writing her Master's thesis about the interaction of epidemic childhood diseases in Amsterdam and Antwerp, 1854-1940.

SESSION 6A

LANGUAGE AND
KNOWLEDGE CIRCULATIONFri 6 March 09.00 - 10.45
Nikolaevsky room*Chair: Gijsbert Rutten, Leiden University**Session coordinator: Amber Zijlma, Leiden University Libraries***LINGUISTIC BORROWINGS AND DIGITAL ARCHIVES: RE-READING
KETELAAR'S VOC RECORDS**

This paper examines a selection of Dutch East India Company (VOC) archival records through the lens of language contact, contextualising a trilingual Dutch–Hindustani–Persian vocabulary compiled by Joan Josua Ketelaar (1659–1718) within his diplomatic correspondence and travel reports.

Ketelaar, a VOC merchant who also served as ambassador to both Mughal and Safavid courts, produced extensive documentation that offers valuable clues about the linguistic strategies employed in cross-cultural diplomacy and trade. His work provides unique insight into how Dutch (proto)colonial officials navigated multilingual environments, adopting local terminology for commodities, administrative positions, and social categories while simultaneously attempting to systematize this knowledge for European audiences.

The paper argues that such linguistic borrowings, and historical code-switching more broadly, provide a productive entry point for writing non-conventional histories of the VOC. They show how merchant communities and local interlocutors co-produced knowledge at the intersection of their respective linguistic repertoires, while also reflecting the asymmetries of colonial mediation: foreign terms were often phonetically assimilated into Dutch, stripped of their original orthography, and explained only when addressing audiences outside Asia. This selective domestication of words, which underscores both shared local knowledge and colonial authority, suggests the emergence of hybrid linguistic communities of practice.

ANNA PYTLOWANY*Independent scholar*

Anna Pytlowany received a PhD in History of Dutch Colonial Linguistics from the University of Amsterdam (2018) with a thesis on J.J. Ketelaar's pioneering Persian and Hindustani grammar. Her research focuses on early modern linguistic encounters, missionary language learning, and the circulation of knowledge within the Dutch East India Company. Publications include a co-edited multidisciplinary volume on the seventeenth-century Dutch Oriental scholar Adriaan Reland, published by Brill (2021).

COLLECTING INFORMATION - THE DUTCH IN MALABAR

This paper examines the information-gathering operations of the Dutch in Malabar during the seventeenth and eighteenth centuries. This is conducted through examining the operations of the Dutch East India Company (VOC) and the non-VOC operations carried out by the Dutch in Malabar. Among the various operations of the VOC, the paper analyses Instructies, Memories van Overgave, Inlandse Dagregisters, and Mallabars Woordenboek. Letters from Malabar by Jacobus Canter Visscher, writing of Joan Nieuhof, Philipus Baldaeus, and Van Linschoten, are evaluated as part of the non-VOC operations. The paper argues that the Dutch conquest of Malabar was simultaneously a conquest of knowledge along with territorial conquest.

ANJANA ABY

Leiden University

Anjana Aby holds an MA in Colonial and Global History from Leiden University. She is a Cosmos Malabaricus Fellow, where she has acquired foundational skills for working with the Dutch East India Company archives to research seventeenth- and eighteenth-century Malabar in India. Her research focuses on information-gathering operations in Malabar, particularly the role of language interpreters within the VOC. She is also involved in the transcription and translation of VOC records to improve their accessibility for wider audiences.

TRACING INTERTEXTUAL COLONIAL LEGITIMACY: THE MEMORANDA OF TRANSFER IN THE VOC ARCHIVES OF THE MOLUCCAS, 1750–1800

The Dutch East India Company (VOC) archives are often read for economic and political information, yet their documentary practices also provide insight into how colonial legitimacy was constructed and transmitted. This paper focuses on the memoranda of transfer written by governors of Ambon and Ternate in the second half of the eighteenth century. Written as practical handbooks for successors, these memoranda were deeply intertextual texts that engaged with Company traditions and earlier colonial writings. Through these intertextual references, the memoranda not only informed new officials but also reproduced and reshaped the VOC's narratives of legitimacy. The potential of the GLOBALISE project becomes crucial here: digitisation and machine-readable transcription (HTR) allow historians to trace patterns of reference, citation, and repetition across a much larger corpus than was previously possible. This paper explores how GLOBALISE enables us to study these patterns systematically, showing how colonial authority was built and maintained through the continuous recycling of texts and ideas within the archive.

PHILIP POST

Utrecht University and Leiden University

Philip Post is a Lecturer in Economic and Social History at Utrecht University. He completed his PhD at Leiden University in 2025 with the dissertation *Constructing Colonial Legitimacy in the Moluccas, 1750–1870*, which examines how Dutch colonial rule was justified and maintained through changing narratives of legitimacy across more than a century. His research focuses on colonial governance, knowledge production, and the construction of authority in the Dutch East Indies. Post has published in journals including *BMGN*, *Itinerario*, and *Diplomatica*.

HOW THE VOC WROTE HOME: MAPPING PARALLEL INFORMATION FLOWS IN THE OBP CORPUS

The documents digitized by GLOBALISE reached the Netherlands as *_Overgekomen Brieven en Papieren_* (OBP): letters and papers received from Asia. Although these documents are often described as having followed a single, centralized route their actual trajectories were far more diverse. Batavia typically collected materials from the various trading posts (*_comptoirs_*) and forwarded a curated selection to Zeeland and Amsterdam. However, several regions including Gamron, Bengal, Coromandel, Malabar, Canton, and Surat, during certain periods maintained direct communication lines to the Netherlands. Meanwhile Colombo intermittently positioned itself as a rival hub to Batavia.

Each forwarding actor made its own decisions about what to copy, forward, or omit, producing document sets shaped by divergent priorities and intended audiences. This division between direct and Batavia-controlled communication streams creates challenges. Digital methods ranging from keyword search in transcription viewers to advanced NLP techniques are complicated by the presence of multiple copies and variant selections of the same information. For historians, it can be difficult to determine how these selection processes impact their research question.

Combining the GLOBALISE transcriptions with their digitized indexes makes it possible to compare these parallel flows of information, revealing the selection biases embedded in their creation and offering new insight into the composition and meaning of the OBP corpus.

KAY PEPPING

Huygens Institute

Kay Pepping graduated in history at Leiden, with a focus on early modern diplomacy and colonial history, including a master's thesis on Dutch East India Company (VOC) negotiations at the local level. Now part of the GLOBALISE project at the Huygens Institute, he combines his interests in digital humanities with his interest in the early modern period.

SESSION 6B

OCEANS OF DATA:
NEW HORIZONSFri 6 March 09.00 - 10.45
Max Nettle room

Chair: Hélder Carvahal, International Institute of Social History
Session coordinator: Tara Huveneers, University of Amsterdam

**PORTUGUESE SHIPS LOST TO DUTCH PRIVATEERING IN ASIA:
BUILDING A DATASET**

Dutch privateering against Portuguese navigation in Asia was a regular activity during most of the first two thirds of the seventeenth century. It began around 1600, with the arrival of the first Dutch ships in Asia, and lasted well into the 1660s, when the recurrent Dutch-Portuguese conflict in the East finally ended. Most of this activity was carried out by the famous Dutch East India Company, or VOC. There have been attempts to compile tables of Portuguese ships lost to Dutch attacks, but they remain limited in scope. This presentation will briefly summarize the existing work and data on the subject and describe the type of dataset that I am currently building to work with this material, based on Portuguese and Dutch sources. It will also describe the state of Portuguese trade and navigation before Dutch privateering began and how it was forced to change in reaction to it, switching from the use of large carracks to fleets of light ships. It will conclude with a tentative comparison with the situation in the Atlantic, where Portuguese navigation was also subjected to considerable pressure by the privateering activities of the Dutch West India Company (WIC), the Atlantic counterpart of the VOC, and other Dutch privateers.

ANDRÉ MURTEIRA

New University of Lisbon

André Murteira is a researcher at CHAM (FCSH, Universidade NOVA de Lisboa, Portugal). He is currently working on an individual research project titled "Ships and War: Dutch and Iberian War Fleets in the Dutch-Iberian Global Conflict (1600-1669)" funded by FCT - Ministério da Educação e Ciência (Portugal) (reference: 2021.02332.CEECIND). His MA dissertation was the basis for his published book, *A Carreira da Índia e o Corso Neerlandês, 1595-1625* (Lisbon: Tribuna da História, 2012). He has a PhD in history from the New University of Lisbon on the subject of Dutch privateering against Portuguese navigation in Asia in the seventeenth century (2016). He has published in journals such as *Journal of Military History*, *Tijdschrift voor Zeegechiedenis*, *Análise Social*, and *Anais de História de Além-Mar*. He co-edited the book *The First World Empire: Portugal, War and Military Revolution* (London: Routledge, 2021).

'[WE] CANNOT EXIST PROPERLY WITHOUT SLAVES': NEW INSIGHTS INTO EARLY DUTCH SLAVE TRADE IN ASIA FROM ESTA DATABASE, 1621-1660

This article examines the early Dutch East India Company (VOC) slave trade in the wider Indian Ocean World (1621–1660) through the expanded 2025 corpus of the Exploring Slave Trade in Asia (ESTA) Database. It demonstrates how the ESTA Database enables the reconstruction of coerced mobility across the Indian Ocean by systematically connecting fragmented archival evidence that has long limited research on slavery in Asia. Combining macro-level database analysis with meso- and microhistorical readings, the article shows how early VOC slave trading relied on a shifting mix of Company initiatives, private trade, tributary obligations, warfare, and raiding networks. ESTA data reveals marked temporal changes, including high-volume shipments in the 1620s, a contraction in the 1630s, and renewed expansion in the 1640s following imperial conquest. The database highlights the centrality of Batavia as a hub, the importance of Coromandel and Arakan as export regions, and evolving shipping patterns and scales of violence. By foregrounding ESTA's relational data model and its capacity to integrate diverse source types, this article underscores the database's value as both a research infrastructure and a foundation for comparative studies of slavery and coerced mobilities across the Indian Ocean and Atlantic worlds.

PASCAL KONINGS

International Institute of Social History and Radboud University Nijmegen

Pascal Konings is project coordinator and junior researcher of the Exploring Slave Trade in Asia (ESTA) project at the International Institute for Social History (IISH) in Amsterdam, and PhD researcher on Matthias van Rossum's ERC-funded project *Voices of Resistance* at the IISH and Radboud University Nijmegen. He obtained a master's degree in History at the University of Amsterdam, researching literacy on the early modern Dutch countryside. His PhD research focuses on patterns and experiences of enslaved maritime mobilities in colonial Dutch Asia during the seventeenth and eighteenth centuries.

BRITT VAN DUIJVENVOORDE

International Institute of Social History

Britt van Duijvenvoorde is a PhD researcher at the International Institute of Social History (IISH) and outreach manager of the Exploring Slave Trade in Asia (ESTA) project. She obtained a master's degree in Philosophy at Radboud University and in History at Leiden University. Her PhD is part of Matthias van Rossum's Vidi project *Resisting Enslavement: A Global Historical Approach to Slavery in the Dutch Atlantic and Asian Empire (1620-1815)*, in which she focuses on how enslaved individuals co-shaped and resisted against enslavability during the seventeenth and eighteenth centuries in the Indian Ocean context.

TESTING THE WATERS: RECONSTRUCTING INTRA-ASIAN MARITIME TRADE NETWORKS IN THE 18TH CENTURY, A PROOF OF CONCEPT

The GLOBALISE corpus contains a unique series of documents, the shipping lists. These lists, spread throughout the Copied Letters, contain detailed records of non-VOC ship movements for over a dozen ports throughout the eighteenth century, and in some cases seventeenth century. Particularly valuable, is that in many cases, these lists also contain detailed personal information on merchants and shipmasters.

The promise of these lists has been well-documented. They have served as the basis for case studies on Makassar, Mocha, and Melaka to name a few (Knaap & Sutherland 2004, Brouwer 1991, Hussin 2007). GLOBALISE provides the opportunity to move beyond port-level case studies. The sheer scale, there are over 2,000 lists, and the amount of manual labour involved in processing them for analysis made this previously impossible. The transcriptions provided by GLOBALISE along with the formulaic nature of the shipping lists make it possible to process them more efficiently. Combining the records from lists across multiple ports enables wider cross-regional analysis of shipping patterns and maritime trade networks. This is particularly valuable as it is precisely at this higher level that the effects of colonial expansion on pre-existing intra-Asian trade networks continues to be debated.

This paper presents preliminary results on two test-cases Melaka and Kochi. It will combine a quantitative analysis of shipping patterns with a qualitative analysis of personal networks emerging from the lists, and show how this approach can be extended for a wider reconstruction.

BRECHT NIJMAN

Huygens Institute and Radboud University Nijmegen

Brecht Nijman is Junior Researcher at the Huygens Institute and an external PhD candidate at Radboud University Nijmegen. She has been with the GLOBALISE project since 2022, where she works within the historical contextualization work package. Brecht has been involved in the creation and curation of contextual data for ships, measures, places and polities, as well as the development of the annotation guidelines for named entities. Her PhD research focusses on the development of early modern intra-Asian maritime trade networks. Brecht holds an MA in History from the University of Edinburgh and an MSc in Applied Data Science for Utrecht University.

UNLOCKING EUROPEAN COLONIAL ARCHIVES: OPEN-SOURCE APPROACHES TO HTR AND COLONIAL ARCHIVES

Digitalisation of colonial archives around the world has enabled new approaches to colonial history. The Globalise transcriptions viewer, for example, has opened up the archives using handwritten text recognition (HTR) to make the Overgekomen Brieven en Papieren (OBP) archive significantly easier to navigate, search, and explore. As part of a collaboration between projects at the International Institute for Social History researching colonial slave trading in Asia, we are working to compliment the work done by the Globalise projects to expand its scope into other colonial archival collections in the Netherlands and beyond. Using Loghi, an open-source HTR tool developed at the Dutch Academy of Arts and Sciences (KNAW), we are developing HTR models for other languages, including early-modern French, Spanish, and Portuguese. These models, to be published in 2026, which make use of the Loghi open-source infrastructure, will be published open-source and free to use.

Currently, in addition to the Globalise OBP corpus, we have fourteen digitised collections from Dutch colonial archives, totalling about one million scans. With the addition to a fifteenth archival collection soon, the total will be closer to two and a half million additional transcribed pages of archival material. This, we intend, will soon be accompanied by French, Portuguese, and Spanish transcribed archival collections as the new HTR models continue to be refined.

In this presentation, I discuss using Loghi and its adaption from Dutch to other languages to facilitate research on slavery and slave trading in Asia. I will also present potential avenues for navigating these digitalised and transcribed archives, using lexical and natural language processing methods. By leveraging these methods, we can begin to find traces of enslaved peoples and their lives in the colonial archives.

BETHANY WARNER

International Institute of Social History

Bethany Warner is a junior researcher for Colonial Archives and Slavery Studies at the International Institute of Social History, Amsterdam. They work at the intersection of historical research, archival studies, and digital humanities. She is working with multiple projects related to colonialism and slave trading in Asia, including Voices of Resistance and The Global Business of Slave Trade. Their current work focuses on developing HTR models for Spanish, Portuguese, and French language material, and digital research methods. Bethany has a research master's degree in History from Utrecht University and a master's degree in Archival and Information Studies from the University of Amsterdam.

SESSION 6C

RECENTERING HISTORIES
AND ARCHIVESFri 6 March 09.00 - 10.45
Posthumus room

Chair: Filipa Ribeiro da Silva, International Institute of Social History
Session coordinator: Jens Aurich, International Institute of Social History

COLLATERAL HISTORY: THE VOC IN CHINA AND JAPAN, 1602–1662

When the Dutch East India Company arrived in the Far East at the beginning of the seventeenth century, the trading company gradually became embroiled in local political changes and conflicts. In other words: when developments in China and Japan altered the landscape for the company's employees operating there, the latter were unable to influence the local situation as they had been able to do elsewhere in Asia. In 1662, the Company learned the hard way that the Taiwan (Formosa) settlement, established specifically for trade with China, had to be abandoned when it was pulled into China's civil strife resulting from the Ming-Qing regime change. (1644–1683). Paradoxically, the VOC's commerce with Japan became completely encapsulated in the Japanese economy when its trading post in Hirado was forcefully transferred to the small island of Dejima in Nagasaki Bay as a result of the maritime prohibition edicts issued by the Shogunate in the late 1639s.

The VOC's story of becoming a pawn of local political and economic developments in the Far East is unique for a couple of reasons.

1. First, early Dutch relations with China and Japan have never been presented as an interconnected whole.
2. Second, the Company had to adapt to local circumstances more than anywhere else because it was a newcomer to the region.
3. Third, this may be especially relevant in the context of the GLOBALISE project because VOC sources align well with a wealth of preserved Chinese and Japanese archival data on the subject.

LEONARD BLUSSÉ

Leiden University

Leonard Blusse is emeritus chair of History of Asian-European Relations, in the History department of Leiden University. He has published, among others, works such as *A Colonial Tragedy, The Chinese Massacre at Batavia, 1740*. Leiden: Leiden University Press 2024, *The Chinese Annals of Batavia, The Kai Ba Lidai Shiji (开吧 历代史记)* and other stories (1610-1795) Leiden: Brill Publishers 2018, and *Visible Cities, Batavia, Canton and Nagasaki and the Coming of the Americans*. Cambridge, Mass: Harvard UP 2008.

THE ZAMORINS AND THE DUTCH: A RITUALISTIC FRAMEWORK OF ENGAGEMENT

This paper explores the ritualistic framework of a Malayalam song titled Keralolpatti Kilippattu that describes the treaty relations between the Zamorin of Calicut and the Dutch in the latter half of the seventeenth century. The song belongs to the Keralolpatti universe of origin legends of Kerala. It traces the origins of the Kerala region to Parasuraman, a figure from the puranas, and attributes the division of the region into minor polities to the legendary ruler Cheraman Perumal. The historical segment of the song focuses on the reign of Bharani Thirunal (Zamorin) and the pan-Kerala Mamankam festival organized by this ruler on the banks of the Pera river in Tirunavay, located on the hinterlands of the Ponnani port. My paper investigates the ritualistic framework of the song by integrating Dutch sources from the period.

RENU ELIZABETH ABRAHAM

O.P. Jindal Global University, India

Dr. Renu Elizabeth Abraham is a historian and Assistant Professor at the Jindal School of International Affairs, O.P. Jindal Global University. She is assistant researcher on the AHRC-DFG funded project "Hindu-Muslim-Jewish Origin Legends in Circulation between the Malabar Coast and the Mediterranean, 1400s–1800s" at the University of Glasgow (<https://himuje-malabar.glasgow.ac.uk>). Her research focuses on the Indian Ocean, the Kerala region, historiography, and the early modern period. She works with Malayalam, Arabic, Portuguese, and Dutch sources.

FORGOTTEN IN THE ARCHIVE, REMEMBERED IN REALITY? MEMORIES OF SLAVE DESCENT IN 18TH CENTURY GALLE, SRI LANKA

How were (and weren't) family histories of enslavement remembered in VOC-ruled Asia? My PhD project, on the lives of freed people and their offspring in early-modern Galle (Sri Lanka), highlights how the descendants of enslaved people eventually merged with local communities. This paper will argue that the VOC archive itself became a site for forgetting, in which freed people and their descendants could obscure their origins. The constant archival (re)production of documents became a mechanism in which formerly enslaved people re-invented their identities. However, outside the paper empire of the Company, memories of someone's slave descent could linger within the social world of the VOC, shedding light on the fact that these archives only comprised a fraction of the reality of these colonial societies. Three case studies from eighteenth-century Galle illustrate that the stigma of slavery could affect someone's societal position for generations. When these cases were brought to court, the VOC often found that they had no clear written record of this history. This made the institution paradoxically an ally in the quest of descendants of freed people to obscure their origins.

POUWEL VAN SCHOOTEN

Leiden University

Pouwel van Schooten is a PhD-candidate at Leiden University, the Netherlands. In 2020 he obtained his Research Master's degree in history from the University of Amsterdam. His ReMa thesis revolved around the reception of Guillaume-Thomas François Raynal's *Histoire des Indes* (1770-1780) in the late eighteenth-century Dutch Republic. As a student he was editor and editor-in-chief of *Skript Historisch Tijdschrift*. After graduating he worked for the Wereldmuseum Amsterdam and was part of a historical climatological research project in collaboration with Tokyo Metropolitan University. Currently he is a member of the larger project titled 'Forgotten Lineages. Afterlives of Dutch Slavery in the Indian Ocean World' headed by prof. dr. Nira Wickramasinghe, financed by the Dutch Research Council. His PhD focusses on the lives of manumitted people and their descendants, specifically their attempts to obscure their enslaved ancestry, in early-modern Galle, Sri Lanka. From 2020 to 2025 he was editorial-assistant for the academic journal *Itinerario. Journal of Imperial and Global Interactions*.

SING ALAP ALAP'S SOLDIERS: MADURESE INFANTRY IN COMPANY SERVICE, 1761-1768

This paper focuses on the service history of a company of Madurese infantry in VOC-service between 1761 and 1769. The company, led first by Masja Alap Alap and after his death at Puttalam in 1763 by Sing Alap Alap served the Dutch company throughout the Dutch-Kandyan war and afterwards on the Coromandel Coast. The paper asks the question if Globalize's transcription viewer allows us to study the VOC's Asian soldiers in more detail than has been possible so far, and what the limitations are of relying on machine-generated searchable transcriptions.

Throughout its history the Dutch East India company relied on soldiers recruited in Asia to flesh out the core of its armies which relied on long-service European regulars. But the Asian troops of the VOC are poorly-studied and understood, in marked contrast to the French and English company armies in India, which relied heavily on Indian-recruited sepoys. The VOC's European personnel can be studied through the VOC's extensive personnel administration, the Asian soldiers do not appear in these centralized accounts. Rather, to understand the lives and service records of the Asian troops requires working through varied mass of sources, a job which could be greatly facilitated by Globalize's searchable transcriptions.

ERIK ODEGARD

International Institute of Social History

Erik Odegard studied history at Leiden University and defended his PhD there in 2018. After teaching at the universities of Leiden and Rotterdam, and fellowships at the National Maritime Museum and the National Archives, Erik was awarded a NWO Veni-grant at the IISH in 2021, focusing on private investors in the Dutch colony in Brazil (1636-1654). From April 2026 onwards, Erik will take up a position as assistant-professor in military history at the Netherlands Defence Academy in Breda.

PRACTICAL INFORMATION

CONFERENCE VENUE

The conference will be held at the International Institute of Social History, a renowned research centre that focuses on labor and social movements across the globe over the past five centuries. It provides sustainable access to information, examine the relationship between work and social inequality and collaborate with societal groups.

The institute is located at the **Cruquiusweg 31, 1019 AT, Amsterdam.**

LEVEL 0

To go to Max Nettlau from the entrance, walk across the lobby, down the steps to Vide, then turn the corner to find the corridor on the lower level.

To go to Posthumus or Scheltema, from the registration desk, go up the stairs and turn to the right. Posthumus and Scheltema are at the end of the corridor.

DINNER VENUE

The dinner on Thursday 5th March will be held at the **Kompaszaal** (KNSM-Laan 311, 1019 LV Amsterdam, Netherlands) from 7.00 pm to 10 p.m. Conference participants and invited guests are requested to wear their conference badges to the venue. Dinner is open to speakers, chairs and invited guests only.

How to get to the dinner at the Kompaszaal

The dinner venue is a 17 minute walk from the IISH. Volunteers will guide conference participants to the venue from two meeting points: the reception of the International Institute of Social History and the reception of the NIU Fender Hotel.

MAP OF SURROUNDINGS

* Note there are roadworks on Veelaan, please plan your journey accordingly.

GoogleMaps:

edu.nl/aw3cr

PROJECT MANAGEMENT & OUTREACH

Arno Bosse (former)
Manjusha Kuruppath
Lodewijk Petram
Matthias van Rossum

Melinda Susanto
Merve Tosun (former)
Leon van Wissen

RESEARCH & DATA

Sophie Arnoult
Sterre Berentzen (former)
Tanne van den Berg
(former)
Femke Brink (former)
Maartje Hids (former)
Gerhard de Kok (former)
Ruben Land (former)

Mrinalini Luthra (former)
Philippe Maillard (former)
Brecht Nijman
Kay Pepping
Pham Thuy Dung
Renate Smit (former)
Stella Verkijk
Henrike Vellinga (former)

TECHNICAL INFRASTRUCTURE

Jarno Bakker
Hennie Brugman
Bram Buitendijk
Sebastiaan van Daalen
QiQing Ding
Maarten van Gompel
Hayco de Jong
Stefan Klut

Rutger van Koert
Meindert Kroese
Bas Leenkegt
Johan List
Martijn Maas
Kerim Meijer
Jona Schlegel
Menzo Windhouwer

EXTERNAL CONSULTANT

Robert Goené

INTERNS

Hannah Goossens (former)	Linda Robertus (former)
Tara Huveneers	Lina de Swaaf
Lija Joseph (former)	Arlette Verdonk (former)
Sailaja Mundakkal (former)	Marc Widmer (former)
Eva Otten (former)	Andy Houwer (former)
Ramin Ravansar (former)	

GUEST RESEARCHERS

Mathijs Boom	Asawari Luthra
Ann Heylen	Leolita Masnun
Simon Kemper	Er-Wen Yang

EXTERNAL COLLABORATORS

Nikhil Bellarykar	Madison MacKenzie
Subham China	Yedda Ljeljeng Ija Palemek
Yeh Chunting	Thalia Rossouw
Johny A. Khusyairi	Roni Tabroni
Paul Phillip van der Linde	

STEERING COMMITTEE

Cátia Antunes	Julia Noordegraaf
Sebastiaan Derks	Piek Vossen
Dirk van Miert	

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Matthias van Rossum	Manjusha Kuruppath
Lodewijk Petram	Brecht Nijman
Melinda Susanto	Kay Pepping
Lina de Swaaf	Pham Thuy Dung
Tara Huveneers	Leon van Wissen
Bethany Warner	Sophie Arnoult
Jona Schlegel	Stella Verkijk

CONFERENCE VOLUNTEERS

Anjana Aby
Ann Heylen
Abmi Handayani
Bart van Duijvenbode
Meenu Rabecca Mathai
Sailaja Mundakkal
Sander Has

SESSION COORDINATORS

Amber Zijlma, Leiden University Libraries
Bente de Leede, Leiden University
Britt van Duijvenvoorde, International Institute of Social History
Jens Aurich, International Institute of Social History
Louie Buana, Leiden University/KITLV
Muhammad Asyraf, Leiden University
Nur'Ain Taha, Utrecht University
Pichayapat Naisupap, Leiden University
Pepijn Trienekens, International Institute of Social History
Ryhan M. Yazid, Kyoto University/KITLV
Vany Susanto, University of Amsterdam

SPECIAL THANKS TO VENUE STAFF

Anne de Jong

Nelson Henrique

Eva van Oene

Rose Spijkerman

PHOTOGRAPHY & VIDEOGRAPHY

Poorvi Garag

Sailaja Mundakkal

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Explorations of GLOBALISE, the Dutch East India Company Archives and the writing of new histories

4 - 6 March 2026

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